

Semi-Automated Technique for Trace Detection of Explosives Using Hyperspectral Sensor

by

Siddharth Chaudhary

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Examination Committee: Dr. Sarawut Ninsawat (Chairperson)
Dr. Tai Nakamura (Co-Chairperson)
Dr. Hiroyuki Miyazaki
Dr. Louis Hornyak

External Examiner: Prof. Song Xianfeng
College of Resources and Environment
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences
Beijing, China

Nationality: Indian
Previous Degree: Master of Technology in Geomatics
Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad, India

Scholarship Donor: Government of Japan

Asian Institute of Technology
School of Engineering and Technology
Thailand
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ABSTRACT

The threat of explosive is increasing due to the large number of conflicts taking place across the world due to which there is an increase in number of warzones. This is a serious issue that is affecting socio-economy of many countries like public security, unused arable land, closing of trade routes, isolation of villages. Such problems act as a hindrance in the development of the country. Frequency of the terrorist activities have increased in the last two decades and leading to a global threat which is challenging the humanity. As reported by AOAV “In 2017 42,972 deaths and injuries were recorded from the use of explosive weapons around the world and of those harmed, 74% (31904) were reported to be civilians”. In 2017 death of civilians was highest with an increase of 38% from 2016 and 165% from 2011. Explosive violence affects dozens of countries around the world. Most of the terrorist attacks use a special type of bomb known as Improvised Explosive Devices (IED) in which the explosives are stored inside metal containers. The explosives are made up of chemical compounds which can have high impact even if used in less quantities. IED’s can be grouped as military, commercial and homemade based on materials used for manufacturing them. These problems motivate the government and research community to develop a technique for fast and accurate detection of explosives. Though there have been number of researches focused on trace detection of chemicals used in explosives where researchers have come up with new techniques like Raman spectroscopy, laser induced breakdown spectroscopy, laser induced fluorescence and ion mobility spectroscopy. But very few works have been done in standoff trace detection using hyperspectral imaging system. The current research techniques used for standoff trace detection involves several difficulties and challenges due to physical properties of the traces.

The aim of this study was to develop a spectral library for different chemicals used in explosives based on their spectral reflectance response, investigate the potential of non-destructive hyperspectral imaging system (I) and accuracy of the model developed using Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) for determining trace detection of explosives. Raman spectroscopy has been used in similar studies, but no study has been published which is based on measurement of reflectance from hyperspectral sensor for trace detection of explosives. I used in this study has an advantage over existing techniques due to its combination of imaging system and spectroscopy, along with being contactless and non-destructive in nature. Hyperspectral images of the chemical were collected using BaySpec hyperspectral sensor which operated in the spectral range of 400 – 1000 nm (144 bands). Image processing was applied on the acquired hyperspectral image to select the region of interest (ROI) and to extract the spectral reflectance of the chemicals which were stored as spectral library. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and first derivative were applied to reduce the high dimensionality of the image and to determine the optimal wavelengths between 400 – 1000 nm. In total, 22 out of 144 wavelengths were selected by analysing the loadings of principal components (PC). SVM was used to develop the classification model. SVM model established on the whole spectrum from 400 – 1000 nm achieved an accuracy of 81.11%, whereas an accuracy of 77.17% with less computational load was achieved when SVM model was established on the optimal wavelengths selected. To determine the suitable altitude, speed of the sensor and minimum mapping unit, the altitude of the sensor was varied from 40cm to 150cm and the MMU was varied from 0.25 to 1cm. The suggested altitude and speed of the sensor was 90cm and 10.5 cm/s. The model achieved an accuracy greater than 70%, whereas 0.25cm to 0.5cm achieved an accuracy less than 60%. The results of the study

demonstrate that hyperspectral imaging system along with support vector machine is a promising tool for trace detection of explosives.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE
	Title Page	i
	Acknowledgements	ii
	Abstract	iv
	Table of Contents	vi
	List of Figures	viii
	List of Tables	x
	List of Abbreviations	xi
1	Introduction	
	1.1 Background	1
	1.2 Statement of the Problem	5
	1.3 Research Questions	6
	1.4 Objectives	7
	1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study	8
	1.6 Structure of Report	8
2	Literature Review	
	2.1 Remote Sensing	10
	2.2 Multispectral and Hyperspectral Sensor	11
	2.3 Interaction of Light Sources with Material	12
	2.4 Hyperspectral Image Data	17
	2.5 Image Distortions in Hyperspectral Remote Sensing Data	18
	2.6 Spectroscopy and Spectral Library	19
	2.7 Hyperspectral Camera, Flying Height and Minimum Mapping Unit	20
	2.8 Existing Methods for Trace Detection of Explosives	22
	2.9 Challenges faced in standoff trace detection	23
	2.10 Related Works on trace detection of chemicals using Hyperspectral Images	25
	2.11 Principal Component Analysis	26
	2.12 Machine Learning for Target Detection	27
	2.13 Summary	32
3	Research Methodology	
	3.1 Overall Methodology	34
	3.2 Software and Hardware Requirements	35
4	Development of Spectral Library for Chemicals used in Explosives	
	4.1 Introduction	37

CHAPTER	TITLE	PAGE
	4.2 Methodology	38
	4.3 Results and Discussions	43
	4.4 Chapter Summary	45
5	Supervised Trace Detection of Explosives using Machine Learning Algorithm	
	5.1 Introduction	47
	5.2 Methodology	47
	5.3 Results	52
	5.4 Discussion	64
	5.5 Chapter Summary	66
6	Determining Suitable Height of Sensor and Minimum Mapping Unit	
	6.1 Introduction	68
	6.2 Methodology	69
	6.3 Results	71
	6.4 Discussion	75
	6.4 Chapter Summary	76
7	Conclusion and Recommendation	
	7.1 Conclusion	77
	7.2 Recommendation	80
	References	82

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
1.1	Classification of explosives	2
1.2	Explosive violence reported from 2011 to 2017	2
1.3	Explosive violence in December 2018 and January 2019	6
2.1	Spectral reflectance curve of vegetation	10
2.2	Spectral reflectance curve for detecting different chemicals	11
2.3	Comparison between Multispectral and Hyperspectral	12
2.4 (a)	Conceptual diagram of passive and active remote sensing	13
2.4 (b)	Interaction of EM waves with atmosphere and material	13
2.5	Spectral intensity of light emitted from a black body on a log-log scale	14
2.6	Spectral Irradiance	17
2.7	Hypersectral Cube	18
2.8	Imaging Specroradiometer	20
2.9 (a)	Conceptual example of traces of chemical present on the soil surface in a petri dish of 4cm diameter	23
2.9 (b)	Conceptual example of a standoff trace detection sensor illustrating key challenges associated with standoff trace explosive chemical detection	24
2.10	Reprojection of original axis	26
2.11	Steps involved in machine learning	27
2.12	Architecture of ANN	28
2.13	Error computation in ANN	29
2.14	Weight calculation in ANN	30
2.15	Architecture of SVM	31
2.16	Architecture of Random Forest	32
3.1	Overall methodology	35
4.1	Flow of Methodology for Objective 1	38
4.2	Laboratory Setup	40
4.3	Field of View	40
4.4	Scanning Angle	40
4.5	Pushbroom Scanning	41
4.6	Methodology for Colleting Light Intensity	42
4.7	Methodology for Validation of Sensor	42
4.8	Developing spectral library	43
4.9	Spectrum of Halogen and Infrared Lamp working together	44
4.10	Distribution of Light Intensity in the FOV	44
4.11	Spectral reflectance of AN, C-4 and TNT	45
5.1	Selection of important wavelength	48
5.2	Architecture of ANN Model	50
5.3	Different activation functions in ANN Model	50
5.4	Methodology for Objective 2	51

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
5.5	Methodology for developing classification model	51
5.6	Cumulative variance of first ten principal components	52
5.7	Absolute loadings for first principal component	53
5.8	Absolute loadings for third principal components	53
5.9	First derivative of spectra	54
5.10	Accuracy assessment of SVM model on full spectra (SVM Model A) and SVM model on optimal wavelength (SVM Model B)	55
5.11	Accuracy assessment of ANN model on full spectra (ANN Model A) and ANN model on optimal wavelength (ANN Model B)	59
5.12	Trace detection of pure chemical and chemical when mixed with soil	61
5.13	Trace detection of pure chemical and chemical when mixed with soil	62
5.14	Comparison of SVM and ANN Model	62
5.15	Comparison of Model using SVM, ANN and RF on Test Dataset	63
5.16	Size of data for different imaging techniques	65
6.1 (a)	Conceptual design for the experiments to be conducted	69
6.1 (b)	Determining suggested altitude of altitude in outdoor conditions	70
6.2	Conceptual design of method to determine suitable MMU for the chemicals used in explosives	70
6.3	Conceptual design of the experiment	71
6.4	Accuracy of chemical at different altitude of sensors	72
6.5	Mapping accuracy for different MMU	72
6.6	Suggested speed for different altitude	73
6.7	Minimum, suggested and maximum speed for different altitude	74

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	TITLE	PAGE
1.1	List of commonly used materials used for manufacturing IED	3
1.2	Physical properties of IED material	4
1.3	Research questions, research objectives and hypothesis	7
2.1	Type of Light Source Available	16
2.2	Standard metadata for spectral library	21
2.3	Application of Hyperspectral Imaging in various fields for determining traces of chemicals	25
3.1	Software Requirements	36
3.2	Lab Requirements	36
4.1	Senor Details	40
4.2	Similarity matrix for different light sources	44
5.1	Variance of individual principal components	52
5.2	Selected optimal wavelength	54
5.3	Classification results of SVM model A	56
5.4	Classification results of SVM model B on optimal wavelengths	56
5.5 (a)	Confusion Matrix of RF model A	57
5.5 (b)	Confusion Matrix of RF model B on optimal wavelengths	57
5.6	Confusion Matrix of ANN model A	58
5.7	Confusion Matrix of ANN model B on optimal wavelengths	59
5.8	Accuracy assessment of ANN model on full spectra (ANN Model A) and ANN model on optimal wavelength (ANN Model B)	59
6.1	Determines the accuracy of chemical at different height of sensors	71
6.2	Determining accuracy for different MMU	72
6.3	Altitude and suggested speed for sensors	73
6.4	Determining speed for various overlapping % at different altitude	74
6.5	Determining number of images, storage and flight time	74

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AAD	Average areal density
AN	Ammonium nitrate
ANN	Artificial neural network
AOAV	Action on armed violence
C4	Composition C-4
CEM	Constrained energy minimization
D2	Deuterium
EM	Electromagnetic
EMD	Empirical mode decomposition
ETM	Enhanced thematic mapper
FOV	Field of view
FWHM	Full width half maximum
GPS	Global positioning system
HS	Hyperspectral
HSI	Hyperspectral imaging system
ICA	Independent component analysis
IED	Improvised explosive device
IMS	Ion mobility spectrometry
IR	Infrared
ISO	International organization for standardization
KNN	K nearest neighbor
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
LIF	Laser-induced fluorescence
MIR	Mid infrared
MMU	Minimum mapping unit
MS	Mass spectrometry
MSS	Multispectral
NIR	Near infrared
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PCA	Principal component analysis
PDF	Probability distribution function
PLS-DA	Partial least squares-discriminant analysis
RF	Random forest
ROI	Region of interest
SERS	Surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy
SVM	Support vector machine
SWIR	Short wave infrared
TH	Tungsten halogen
TNT	Trinitrotoluene
UAV	Unarmed vehicle
UV	Ultraviolet
VIS	Visible

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Frequency of the terrorist activities have increased in the last two decades and leading to a global threat which is challenging the humanity. Many terrorist attacks use a special type of bomb known as Improvised Explosive Devices (IED) in which the explosives are stored inside metal containers. The explosives are made up of chemical compounds which can create high impact even if used in less quantities. IED's can be grouped as military, commercial and homemade on the basis of materials used for manufacturing them. Homemade explosive mixtures can be prepared by mixing inorganic energetic oxidant salts (Ammonium nitrate, Potassium nitrate, Potassium chlorate) with fuel like petrol, diesel, charcoal etc. (M. Marshall et al., 2009). The oxidant salts mentioned above are easily available in market in the form of fertilizers. Ammonium nitrate (AN) is one of the most commonly used fertilizers for agricultural purpose and combination of this with fuel can result in Ammonium Nitrate Fuel Oil (ANFO), dynamites that are explosive compounds. Similarly, Potassium Nitrate is a widely used fertilizer, but it is also used for manufacturing firecrackers by mixing it with blackpowder. Chemicals like ammonium nitrate, tri nitro toluene, C4 are used as explosive material. Ammonium nitrate is one of most common fertilizer used for agriculture but a mixture of ammonium nitrate and fuel oil in the ratio of 94:6 results in an explosive which is used widely. This type of bomb is gaining a lot of popularity as it can be manufactured using commonly available material at home (J. Yinon et al., 2007, M. Marshall et al., 2009, R.S. Golightly et al., 2009, N. Nuntawong et al., 2013, C. Martín-Alberca et al., 2014, M.A.Fernándezdel et al., 2014, A.Hakonen et al., 2015,2016, P.R.Laska et al., 2016). In recent years, across the globe some major terrorist attacks were noticed in Pakistan, Brussels, Nigeria (2016), Paris (2015), Boston (2013) in which IED were widely used. IED is becoming an ideal weapon for spreading terrorism due to its special features like ease of manufacture at low cost and it can be designed in various sizes and forms making it difficult to be detected.

The threat of explosive is increasing due to the large number of conflicts taking place across the world due to which there is increase in number of warzones. This is a serious issue that is affecting socio-economy of many countries like public security, unused arable land, closing of trade routes, isolation of villages. Such problems act as a hindrance in the development of the country. These problems motivate the government and research community to develop a technique for fast and accurate detection of explosives.

An explosive is device which produces high amount of energy in a very less span of time when they are exposed to heat or friction. Sudden increase in pressure and temperature is observed when energy is released due to which all materials are transformed into hot compressed gas. These compressed gases generate a shock wave in the nearby medium because of its rapid expansion due to its high pressure and temperature. Different types of explosives are shown in the Figure 1.1, they can be categorized as high energy and low energy based on speed at which they expand. High explosive is further subdivided into primary, secondary and tertiary explosive based on their sensitivity. Whereas low explosives undergo burning, it means it can detonate only under extreme conditions.

Figure 1.1: Classification of explosives (M. Lopez-Lopez et al., 2014)

Figure 1.2: Explosive violence reported from 2011 to 2017

Source: “Action on armed violence <https://aoav.org.uk/>”

As reported by AOAV “In 2017, 42,972 deaths and injuries were reported from the use of explosive weapons around the world and of those harmed, 74% were reported to be civilians – 31,904”. In 2017 death of civilians was highest with an increase of 38% from 2016 and 165% from 2011 as shown in Figure 1.2. Many countries around the world are affected due to explosive violence, but there are few countries which witness high occurrence air bombings, terrorist activities using IED.

According to AOAV's report top ten 'hottest spots' of explosive violence from the year 2011 to 2017 throughout the world are:

1. Syria
2. Iraq
3. Pakistan
4. Afghanistan
5. Yemen
6. Nigeria
7. Somalia
8. Gaza
9. Libya
10. Turkey

Table 1.1: List of commonly used materials used for manufacturing IED

Explosive Component	Description/Availability	Explosive Type
Hydrogen Peroxide	Available at medical stores	IED
Acetone	Available at the polish remover and can be a material in plastic creation	IED
Ethyl Alcohol	Also known as ethanol, it is available at medical stores	IED
Methyl Alcohol	It is a lite volatile flammable element, this element as antifreeze, it is known as methanol	IED
Hexamine	This chemical extracted from the white cool available at supermarkets	IED
Sodium acid	Available in medical stores	IED
Sodium Nitrate	Found at agriculture stores	IED
Ammonium Nitrate, Barium Nitrate, Lead Nitrate	Available at agriculture stores	IED
Potassium Nitrate	Also known as nitrate available at agriculture stores	IED
Sodium carbonate	It is used to make papers and glasses, known as washing soda	IED

Sodium Bicarbonate	A white soluble compound	IED
Potassium Chlorate	Known as bleaching agent	IED
Nitrobenzene	Oily high toxic water, used for screen cleaning	IED
Hydrazine Hydrate	Can be found in sponges	IED

Table 1.1 gives list of the most commonly used materials for manufacturing the IED and also describes the availability of these materials. Whereas Table 1.2 gives information regarding the physical form of the IED materials used and main parts of the IED. Explosive material used in IEDs are generally packed in plastic or metal containers.

Table 1.2: Physical properties of IED material

IED Material	Placement in IED	Physical Form
Ammonium Nitrate	Used as blasting material in IEDs	Solid State
Trace tone	Mixed with the IED to deliver extra effect	Solid state
Ethylene Glycol Nitrate	Component in the low freezing dynamite	Liquid Material
C4	High power military explosives, used in IED as a blasting material	Solid state

Standoff trace detection is a method in which the operator or the sensor does not have a physical contact with explosive and therefore this technology provides for a better capability for different architectures of security. Some of the potential techniques to detect traces of explosive material are laser based spectroscopic techniques which include raman spectroscopy (RS), laser induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), resonant raman spectroscopy, laser induced fluorescence (LIF), ion mobility spectrometry and hyperspectral remote sensing (P.M. Pellegrino et al., 2015, Edelman. G et al., 2012). LIBS is considered as a destructive technique and therefore it is not recommended to be used on human and vehicles. Since the laser beam used in this technique is pointed at a specific spot; it becomes more time consuming and difficult to scan large area in real conditions (J.L. Gottfried et al., 2008). One of the most commonly used technique for trace detection is Ion mobility spectrometry (IMS). Although it is a successful technique it faces drawbacks like false alarm rate, matrix effects, instability in response and use of physical molecular structure for detection (J.S. Caygill et al., 2012). To minimize the risk of destruction and contamination of traces Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) is most suitable as it provides contactless identification of evidence. HSI is an integration of spectroscopy and digital imaging technique to create a dataset which gives information about target in three dimensions i.e. spatial and spectral.

Hyperspectral satellite images were conventionally used for remote sensing applications for earth science but later it found its application in different fields like medicines, food science, forensics and medical analysis. Hyperspectral images are acquired at a narrow spectral band which are collection or stack of images (Edelman. G et al., 2012). HSI can be operated in different EM spectrum ranging from UV to infrared similar to spectroscopy. HSI has an advantage over other techniques due to its fast rate of data acquisition, non-destructive nature toward samples, less sample preparation, reducing human error and better illustration of results. Chemicals like ammonium nitrate, tri nitro toluene, C4 are used as explosive material. Ammonium nitrate is one of most common fertilizer used for agriculture but a mixture of ammonium nitrate and fuel oil in the ratio of 94:6 results in an explosive which is used widely.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The threat of explosives is increasing due to the large number of conflicts taking worldwide and increasing number of war zones. This has become a major problem of concern as many countries will be affected in coming future. At the end of any destructive event most affected ones are children and the innocent civilians of the society. As discussed in (Gebremichael T. Tesfamariam et al., 2012) and (Esam M.A. Hussein et al. , 2000) explosives don't have fixed place where we can find them it can be placed on the surface or buried under the ground or can be cluttered with different materials or covered by plants. Explosives can be found in various environmental conditions like in sandy area, mountains, forest and in urban areas as highlighted in (David J. Daniels et al., 2008). Presence of explosive gives rise to many social economic problems like many routes used for trades are closed, lands which are arable are unused and many villages gets isolated from the society and results in a threat to food security. Figure 1.3 shows the number of total incidents in December 2018 and January 2019 across the globe.

LIBS is considered as a destructive technique and therefore it is not recommended to be used on human and vehicles. Since the laser beam used in this technique is pointed at a specific spot; it becomes more time consuming and difficult to scan large area in real conditions (J.L. Gottfried et al., 2008). One of the most commonly used technique for trace detection is Ion mobility spectrometry (IMS). Although it is a successful technique it faces drawbacks like false alarm rate, matrix effects, instability in response and use of physical molecular structure for detection (J.S. Caygill et al., 2012). LIF works on the principal of decomposing the molecules into characteristic fragments (C. Wynn et al., 2011, J. White et al., 2011). But LIF can detect only nitrogen containing explosive and require a laser source which can be tuned to different wavelength which result in thermal degradation of samples (C. Wynn et al., 2010). Many scientists and engineers from industry and academia have been working on implementing standoff trace detection method on different applications (D.S. Moore et al., 2004, S. Wallin et al., 2009, A.W. Fountain et al., 2014, M. Lopez-Lopez et al., 2014, P.M. Pellegrino et al., 2015, K.E. Brown et al., 2016, K.L. Gares et al., 2016, S. Elbasuney et al., 2016) but no technology has emerged as an optimum technique yet. Methods which are used today to scan suspicious objects on bomb site still have the operators at risk due to their close contact with the target (J. Yinon et al., 2007, M. Marshall et al., 2009, R.S. Golightly et al., 2009, N. Nuntawong et al., 2013, C. Martín-Alberca et al., 2014, Fernández de la et al., 2014, A. Hakonen et al., 2015, 2016, P.R. Laska et al., 2016). Though there have been number of researches focused on trace detection of chemicals used in explosives where researchers have come up with new techniques like RS, LIBS, LIF and IMS. But very few works have been done

in standoff trace detection using hyperspectral imaging system. The current research techniques used for standoff trace detection involves several difficulties and challenges due to physical properties of the traces. But major key challenges are average area density for trace chemicals, area covered by traces as compared to background material. Hyperspectral sensor acquires spectral response of the target materials in hundreds of bands. HSI is techniques which overcomes the above-mentioned drawbacks and also provide advantages like high sensitivity, minimize risk of operators, non-destructive technique, portable to crime scene which is required by defence research organizations and forensic departments. This research helps to develop spectral library based on reflectance responses for different chemicals used in explosives. But along with all these advantages HSI faces the curse of dimensionality, the spectral responses of the target material are saved in hundreds of bands and many neighbouring bands are highly correlated due to which there is repetition of information. In this research efficient method will be determined to reduce the dimensionality of the hyperspectral data. HSI has been used in several applications for food quality, agriculture, detecting macronutrients, forensic science but trace detection of explosives using HSI and machine learning algorithms is in itself an original work. Therefore, the research and its outcome will work as the baseline work for such types of research. A method for trace detection of chemicals without getting in contact with the ground will be a prominent asset for the defence. This will be a starting point to extend approach for other type of chemicals and different conditions.

Figure 1.3: Explosive violence in December 2018 and January 2019

Source: “Action on armed violence <https://aoav.org.uk/>”

1.3 Research Questions

1. What is the spectral signature of pure explosives residues when distributed in the soil?
2. How hyperspectral sensor can be used to study spectral reflectance of chemicals used in explosives?
3. What is the most suitable range of wavelength for analysis detection of chemicals present in explosives?
4. What should be the suitable height, speed of the platform and minimum mapping unit so that the feature extraction/ target detection becomes more accurate?
5. Which algorithm should be used for trace detection of the explosive in the hyperspectral image?

1.4 Objectives

1.4.1 Overall Objective

The overall objective of the research is to determine the probable areas where explosives can be present by identifying the traces of the chemicals using hyperspectral remote sensing data.

Specific Objectives

1. To create a spectral library for different available pure explosives like TNT, C4, ANFO using hyperspectral sensor.
2. Determining a suitable algorithm for detection and identification of explosives and classification of a region most likely to contain explosives.
3. To determine the suitable wavelength, minimum mapping unit, speed and flying height in which traces of explosives can be detected when the sensor is on UAV.

Table 1.3: Research questions, research objectives and hypothesis

Research Questions	Research Objectives	Hypothesis
<p>What is the spectral signature of pure explosives residues when distributed in the soil?</p> <p>How chemical composition of various explosives affects the spectral reflectance obtained from hyperspectral sensor?</p> <p>Which is the most suitable range of wavelength for analysis detection of presence of chemicals used in explosives?</p>	<p>To create a spectral library for different available explosives like TNT, C4, ANFO lying under different conditions using hyperspectral sensor.</p>	<p>Soil disturbances i.e mixture of chemicals with soil in different quantity helps in identifying the explosives.</p> <p>Chemicals of various explosives show different spectral reflectance and chemical structure plays an important role in the spectral reflectance. These chemicals can be detected in NIR.</p>
<p>What should be the suitable altitude of the platform carrying hyperspectral sensor, minimum mapping unit so that detection of chemical traces becomes more accurate?</p>	<p>To determine the best wavelength, suggested minimum mapping unit, speed and altitude of the sensor.</p>	<p>Lower the height of the platform we will be able to get more accurate results.</p>
<p>Which algorithm should be used for classifying the image?</p>	<p>Determining a suitable algorithm for trace detection of explosives.</p>	<p>SVM, ANN and RF are suitable algorithms to classify the image and identify the chemical residues of explosives because the use of</p>

		correlation matrix in above algorithms may be easier to be implemented in near real-time processing
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1.5 Scope and Limitations of the Study

The scope of this research is to identify the traces of chemicals like TNT, C4, and ANFO which are used. The proposed research uses a BaySpec Hyperspectral sensor to collect hyperspectral imagery of the chemicals placed under different condition in the laboratory and generate the spectral library for the chemicals used in explosives. The initial setup of the research was indoor and daylight lightning conditions was created using different artificial light sources. The study investigates the technique for reducing the dimensions of the hyperspectral data and classifying the imagery into target sites and background sites which help in detection of chemicals. Ground sampling distance of the sensor during the laboratory can reach up to 0.12 mm when placed at a height of 40cm. The significance of the research is that a spectral library is created for the chemicals used in explosives along with an appropriate method for reducing the dimension of hyperspectral imagery and detection of the chemicals in the image. The library which is created is limited to the chemicals which are been used for explosions in Thailand. This research is using hyperspectral sensor operating in the range of 400-1000nm where electromagnetic rays cannot penetrate the ground unlike microwave and therefore the research is more focused on studying the spectral response of the chemicals for identification of chemical traces. Determining the coordinates of the target sites is beyond the scope of this study as the sensor is not installed with GPS.

The BaySpec hyperspectral sensor and the chemicals which are required for completing the research will be provided by the organization called Foundation Innovation for Happiness. The chemicals provided by the foundation are TNT, C4 and ANFO along with the soil samples and the metal containers from the fields where explosives were present.

1.6 Structure of Report

This dissertation report submitted is structured into seven chapters and reference chapter.

Chapter 1 discusses about the general background of the explosives and existing techniques for trace detection of explosives and its drawback, including the statement of the problem, objectives and the scope of the study.

Chapter 2 mainly focuses on interaction of electromagnetic waves with materials, different types of external light sources available, advantages of hyperspectral data and processing of the data, reviews of the past research related to trace detection of explosives and application of hyperspectral remote sensing in different research fields.

Chapter 3 presents the overall methodology adopted for completion of the specific objectives of this study and gives description about hardware and software required during the study.

Chapter 4 discuss spectral responses of different chemical used in explosives and development of the spectral library.

Chapters 5 highlight the issue of dimensionality in hyperspectral data and presents the classification model developed using several machine learning algorithms for trace detection of explosives.

Chapters 6 presents the analysis for selecting the optimum height of the sensor and minimum mapping unit to improve the accuracy of the model.

Chapter 7 provides the discussions, conclusions, and recommendation followed by references and bibliography.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Remote Sensing

The term remote sensing can be defined as “the science of acquiring, processing, and interpreting images that record the interaction between the electromagnetic energy and matter” (Sabins, 1996). Remote sensing involves acquiring information about an object by help of sensor which are not in physical contact with the object and gives knowledge regarding the environment by measuring electromagnetic radiations or acoustic energy. Various instruments used for acquiring data used are radiometer, spectrometer, camera, radar, thermal devices and other instruments (IIRS, 2005) The basic components of an ideal remote sensing are: “uniform energy source, non-interfering atmosphere, energy-matter interactions at the earth’s surface, sensor, real time data processing and supply system, multiple data users”.

2.1.1 Spectral Reflectance

Electromagnetic radiation from the sun is reflected or absorbed by different materials or earth surfaces in different ways. Physical and chemical properties of these materials are important factors which determine the reflectance. Reflectance of the surface is a function of wavelength of electromagnetic energy. Therefore, every material have unique spectral reflectance which makes it possible to be identified based on the spectral reflectance signatures. Spectral reflectance of objects is represented graphically as a function of wavelength in spectral reflectance curve. Spectral reflectance curve of vegetation is shown in Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1: Spectral reflectance curve of vegetation

Spectral reflectance signatures are generated due to reflection or absorption from the target or the surface. In spectral signature of vegetation, it is observed that leaf pigments have dominance in the spectrum range of 400-700 nm and less absorption is noticed in 500-600 nm due to which a healthy vegetation appears green in color. On the other hand, stressed vegetation shows different spectral response due to stress in the pigments. Stress detection in the plants are studied using the wavelength between NIR and red also known as red edge. Soil is characterized using the MIR (1300-2500 nm) and similarly if leaf has high water content a low reflectance can be observed at

1400nm, 1900 nm. The examples of spectral signatures of different chemicals are shown in Figure 2.2. Mapping of silicate materials like garnets, feldspars and other non-hydroxylated minerals can be mapped using hyperspectral datasets. (e.g., Feng et al., 2018; Hecker et al., 2010; Riley and Hecker, 2013). Detecting and quantifying rock forming minerals is essential to differentiate and classify igneous, metamorphic, and sedimentary lithologies, (e.g., Aslett et al., 2018; Hecker et al., 2012)

Figure 2.2: Spectral reflectance curve for detecting different chemicals
(Source: Hecker et al., 2019)

2.2 Multispectral and Hyperspectral Sensor

Reflectance of a surface or a material are measured using two types sensors (a) Multispectral and (b) Hyperspectral. These sensors are used in three most common ways; placed either in UAV/aircraft, satellites or hand-held spectrometers.

Multispectral sensors records the reflected electromagnetic energy over a range of relatively narrow for covering the visible to near infrared spectrum. Due to a smaller number of bands the spectral resolution of the sensors are low resulting in very low discrimination power. Examples of multispectral satellite sensors are Landsat, Spot and IRS satellites and example of multispectral sensors for UAV are Sentera Quad, Parrot Sequoia, MicaSense RedEdge.

Whereas hyperspectral sensors is a stack of large number of images acquired at different wavelengths and record the reflected energy in hundreds of contiguous spectral narrow bands. Most of the space borne imaging spectrometers or hand-held spectrometers have spectral

resolution of 5-10 nm and measure the reflectance in the spectrum of 350-2560 nm. The contiguous narrow bands gives continuous spectral response of the material across the whole spectrum of electromagnetic wave due to hyperspectral data is sensitive towards slight variation of reflected energy. Comparison between the spectral responses collected from multispectral and hyperspectral is shown in Figure 2.3. In the figure it can be observed that the spectral reflectance of sample selected is more continuous in hyperspectral as compared to multispectral image and giving more information.

Figure 2.3 Comparison between Multispectral and Hyperspectral (Harrisgeospatial.com, 2019)

2.3 Interaction of Light Sources with Material

2.3.1 Active and Passive Remote Sensing

Based on light source remote sensing can be classified as active and passive remote sensing and similarly instruments can also be passive sensors and active sensors. Passive sensors collect reflected energy or the energy emitted from the target. These sensors can sense the emitted radiation by the object in the field of view or record the reflectance from an object due to an external source of energy. Passive instruments sense the radiation from reflected sunlight which is a common external source. On the other hand, active sensors illuminate their target. The concept of passive and active remote sensing is shown in Figure 2.4(a) and interaction of EM wave with atmosphere and material is shown in Figure 2.4(b).

Figure 2.4(a): Conceptual diagram of passive and active remote sensing

Figure 2.4(b): Interaction of EM waves with atmosphere and material

2.3.2 Sunlight as Light Source

Temperature of sun reaches over 20million degree because of nuclear fusion reaction taking place in which hydrogen is converted into helium. Hydrogen atoms which are present at the surface of the of the sun absorbs the radiations making it not visible, the heat is transferred through convection. High amount of energy is released from the sun and and a fraction of it reaches on earth in the form of light. Sunlight is a form of "electromagnetic radiation" and the visible light that we see is a small subset of the electromagnetic spectrum. "A photon is characterized by either a wavelength, denoted by λ or equivalently an energy, denoted by E ". Energy of photon is has an inverse relationship with the wavelength of light as shown in Equation 2.1:

$$E = (hc)/\lambda \quad (\text{Equation 2.1})$$

where,

" h is Planck's constant and c is the speed of light.

$$h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ joule}\cdot\text{s} ; c = 2.998 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}''$$

Blackbody is defined as a body which has a property to absorb all the energy incident on it and emits the energy according to the temperature of the body. Many light sources are available which are modelled like blackbody emitters. The name is derived due to its property of appearing black in visible range if it doesn't emit any radiation and absorbs all. Spectral intensity of light emitted from black body on a log scale is shown in Figure 2.5 The spectral irradiance from a blackbody is given by Planck's radiation law, shown in the following Equation 2.2:

$$F(\lambda) = \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\lambda^5 \left(\exp\left(\frac{hc}{k\lambda T}\right) - 1 \right)} \quad (\text{Equation 2.2})$$

where:

“ λ is the wavelength of light; T is the temperature of the blackbody (K); F is the spectral irradiance in $\text{Wm}^{-2}\mu\text{m}^{-1}$; and h, c and k are constants”

The total power density from a blackbody is determined by integrating the spectral irradiance over all wavelengths which gives:

$$H = \sigma T^4 \quad (\text{Equation 2.3})$$

“where σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature of the blackbody in kelvin.

Figure 2.5 Spectral intensity of light emitted from a black body on a log-log scale

2.3.3 External Light sources

Hyperspectral imaging system acquires the image of the sample based on the amount of light reflected. To achieve this proper illumination from light sources are required to carry out experiments. If the experiment which needs to be conducted is inside laboratory or in the indoor conditions in such cases external light sources are required. Different light sources have different spectrum for illumination and can be selected based on the application and on the receiving spectrum of the sensor. Some of the external light sources are discussed below.

- **Tungsten-Halogen (TH)**

TH lamp is most commonly used light source to cover visible and near infrared spectrum in spectroscopic applications. These lamps have tungsten filaments with fused silica and an active halogen gas like bromine. Its popularity in the spectroscopic applications for measuring reflectance is due to its stable and smooth spectral output. The dominant spectrum is from 350 nm to 900nm depending on the color temperature of each lamp.

- **Deuterium (D2)**

Spectroscopic applications which are operated in UV range uses D2 light source. Stable electric arc is maintained in the D2 atmosphere due to which these lamps generate intense UV radiation. The spectral intensity of D2 lamp ranges continuously from 160 to 400 nm. Since the arc maintains stable and uniform continuous light intensity it makes D2 lamps useful UV light source for analytical instruments.

- **Xenon (Xe)**

Xe is light source which covers the spectrum of UV, visible and NIR and therefore used for spectroscopic applications using UV, visible or NIR spectroscopy. The spectrum obtained in visible range as compared to another available light source is relatively flat. The Xe light source available is light weight and compact making it suitable for spectroscopy and optical scanning. Depending upon the type of bulb Xe can cover spectrum ranging from 185-2200nm and 320-2200nm.

- **Incandescent Bulbs**

Tungsten filament present in the incandescent bulb gets heated when a stable current is conducted through it. The bulbs are generally filled with argon gas to prevent the burning of tungsten wire. Visible light is emitted from the bulb at a temperature around 2000K. The heat generated in the filament is transported to the surroundings through radiation, convection, and conduction. Incandescent bulb emits more of red light as compared to daylight. Emissions are even recorded in infrared spectrum.

- **Fluorescent Bulbs**

Fluorescent lamp is made up of mercury and argon which is filled in a glass tube. Nonequilibrium discharge is created inside the tube due to which there is difference of temperature between surrounding of gas and electron. Visible light is produced by two mechanisms: “optical emission directly from the discharge, or by exciting phosphors on the surface of the tube”.

Table 2.1 Type of Light Source Available

Type	Wavelength Range (nm)	Application
Colour/VIS/NIR	360-2500	Tungsten Halogen
DUV	190-400	Deuterium
UV	215-400	Deuterium
UV/VIS/NIR	215-2500	Deuterium/Halogen
UV/VIS	200-1000	Xenon
Fluorescence	Multiple	LED

(b)

Figure 2.6: (a) Spectral irradiance of halogen, mercury, xenon and solar light (b) Intensity of daylight, incandescent, fluorescent, halogen, cool and warm white LED (c) Spectral intensity

(Zeiss-campus.magnet.fsu.edu, 2019)

2.4 Hyperspectral Image Data

The hyperspectral image data is acquired using two scanning mechanisms (a) whiskbroom (b) pushbroom. In whiskbroom mechanism sensors work like a whisk broom so the sensor sweeps back and forth across the entire swath to collect data whereas in pushbroom sensors view across the entire swath at once, building strips of data like a pushbroom. Dwell time of the sensors in this approach is more due to no moving parts in pushbroom. The instrument has other advantages like less weight and compact as compared to whiskbroom instruments but due to large number of detectors present the complexity of calibration increases.

Spectral response of the material for different spectral channels is represented in the form of an image composed of pixels as shown in Figure 2.7. The data collected in continuous narrow bands which can be up to several hundred in the electromagnetic spectrum forms a Hyperspectral image. Spectrally and it emerged as a promising technology in remote sensing for studying earth surface materials by two ways spectrally & spatially (Tong Q et al. 2001). This technology is also called image spectroscopy as it is a single system comprising of imaging and spectroscopy. Since data is collected in contiguous bands the amount of data produced is vast. Hyperspectral data has an advantage over multispectral data for identifying the features on the earth based on physical and chemical properties due to its high spectral resolution while higher spatial resolution helps in locating those materials (Gross and Schott, 1998). For understanding the spectral characteristics of the material the spectral signature of a single pixel obtained from hyperspectral data can be used which is also similar to a laboratory quality spectrum obtained by a spectroradiometer.

The major applications of hyperspectral remote sensing are in the field of atmosphere (Hou et al., 2017), organic materials (Sohara et al., 2010), ecology (Crabtree, 2005), geology (Xu, Chen and Meng, 2019), coastal waters (Bajjouk et al., 2019), snow algae and impurities (Huovinen, Ramírez & Gómez, 2018), estimation of biomass (Duan et al., 2012), detection of petroleum hydrocarbons

(Scafutto, de Souza Filho & de Oliveira, 2017), agriculture (Gao et al., 2019), food quality assessment (Yao et al., 2019) and mapping of forest (Sun, Cao & Sanchez-Azofeifa, 2019). Chemicals like iron oxides, sulphates, quartz, chlorites can be mapped using hyperspectral remote sensing (Cudahy, 2002). Therefore, hyperspectral have high capability for target detection, mineral mapping, detection of chemicals present in soils.

Figure 2.7: Hyperspectral Cube

2.5 Image Distortions in Hyperspectral Remote Sensing Data

The hyperspectral images are acquired by the help of sensors mounted on UAV, aircraft or satellites and are of raster format/digital format. Digital image processing is applied on the dataset for interpretation and analysis. The acquired images contain errors which are categorised as atmospheric, instrumental and geometric distortion.

2.5.1 Atmospheric Distortions

The transmission of electromagnetic radiation gets attenuated due scattering and absorption caused by molecules and aerosols in the atmospheres which results in addition of error in the hyperspectral data. Radiance (L) can be calculated using the brightness value stored in every pixel of the image. Solar radiance can be calculated using the equation 2.4 if there is absence of atmosphere (Jacobsen Anne et al. 2001):

$$L = E\Delta\lambda * \cos\theta * \Delta\lambda * R / \pi \quad \text{Equation 2.4}$$

where “L is the radiance available for measurement, $E\Delta\lambda$ is the average spectral irradiance in the band $\Delta\lambda$, R is surface reflectance and π accounts for the upper hemisphere of solid angle (Richards et al. 1999)”.

2.5.2 Instrumental Distortions

Instrumental distortions occur due to faulty calibration of sensors or scanner construction. Incorrect sensor calibration leads to radiometric errors due to which incorrect brightness value is recorded for the pixels. Incorrect measurement can be part of spectral band or spectral response within the pixel (Larsen R et al. 1997). Sensor which is going to be used must be radiometrically calibrated and it is achieved by taking precise radiance measurement with correct units

($\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2/\text{sr}/\text{nm}$) and conversion to digital number. Striping or banding is another form of instrumental error which results in visible noise pattern.

2.5.3 Geometric Distortions

Remote sensing data acquired from sensors having large FOV at low altitude tend to have geometric distortion. This distortion results into smaller pixel size at nadir as compared to pixel size at the edges of swath (Richards et al. 1999). The size of the pixel in a scan direction at scan angle θ is given by

$$p\theta = \beta h \sec^2\theta = p \sec^2\theta \quad \text{Equation 2.5}$$

where “ β is the instantaneous field of view (IFOV), h is the altitude, and p is the pixel direction at nadir”

2.5.4 Noise Modelling

Noise removal from the hyperspectral image is the most important step and this can be implemented using digital image processing techniques. Image induced with noise can degrade the quality to an extent where important information cannot be extracted. Noise in remote sensing data can be categorized into random and periodic noise. Uncorrelated noise is most commonly induced in the image, this type of noise can be eliminated using image processing. In terms of a spatially-sampled image, uncorrelated noise is defined as “the random grey level variations within an image that has no spatial dependence from pixel to pixel”. PDF or histogram are used to characterizes the noise.

2.6 Spectroscopy and Spectral Library

Reflectance based spectral signatures of the earth surface or target materials are retrieved by using spectral radiance measured by field spectroscopy. As compared to satellite imaging spectroscopy, UAV imaging spectroscopy or sensing instrument has an advantage in field as it can be fixed over the target of interest for longer period of time due to which length of the path between the sensor and the object gets reduced.

Currently available spectroradiometers are portable and rugged type which have evolved from non-imaging spectrometers which were commonly used in laboratories. Two types of field spectroradiometers are available:

1. Small, operate in visible and NIR (350-1000 nm), Signal to Noise (250:1)
2. Large and heavier, operate in entire solar spectrum, Signal to Noise (1000:1)

Sampling interval of the spectroradiometer can be varied from 1nm to 10 nm depending upon the application. Most common configuration is 3nm at FWHM for VNIR, 10nm for SWIR and for few specific applications like fluorescence measurement it is set to 1nm in VNIR.

Figure 2.8: Imaging Spectroradiometer (Techexpo.com, 2019)

In recent years Spectral radiance measurement has been widely used. This technique uses the supplied fiber optics bundle which also has an option to attach different optics for Field of View (FOV) variation. Hyperspectral imagers used in spectroscopy has emerged as a relevant and promising tool, although it faces certain drawbacks of scale and non linear effects which needs to be fixed. (Buddenbaum et al., 2012). Single beam is most commonly used to acquire near ground reflectance, in this method reflectance of the target sample and calibration panel is measured using the same instrument. Standard calibration panels like spectralon are manufactured by (Labsphere, North Sutton, NH, USA). Handheld spectroradiometers are generally used to take the measurements in the field. To automate the process of measurement and remove the human error UAV are tested. Use of UAV will provide fast measurement and automation but will be challenging at the same time (Hruska et al., 2012).

A collection of spectral response which characterizes the reflectance i.e. spectral response of target materials and surface are called as Spectral Library. It can be built in the simplest way by calculating the mean spectral response and then apply the standard deviation on the measured target to collect end members (Hueni et al., 2011). Moreover, more complex cases can also include the spatiotemporal variation of a surface or material which in turn characterizes properties of different type or conditions. The presence of well-documented metadata on spectral libraries enhances the suitability as well as long-term usability, and quality assurance of data from other researchers. In (Rashaih et al., 2014) one of the most important field spectroscopy metadata was highlighted by advanced users, and (Jimenez et al., 2014) introduced an approach to establish a standard metadata system for field spectroscopy based on ISO and OGC standards as shown in Table 2.2.

2.7 Hyperspectral Camera, Flying Height and Minimum Mapping Unit

The OCI™-F push-broom hyperspectral cameras (the brand name, OCI, is inspired from “All-seeing Eye”) are high-performance, ultra-miniaturized hyperspectral imaging engines, packed with SuperSpeed USB 3.0 interface. They feature dramatic reduction in size and weight and increased data transfer rates. These hyperspectral cameras acquire VIS-NIR hyperspectral data with continuous spectral and spatial coverage. The OCI™-F features “true push-broom” fast

hyperspectral imaging, simply by using your hand to move the imager or sample. Compactness, simple operation, and intuitive software make the OCI™-F imagers very straightforward for applications such as precision agriculture, remote sensing, forensics, and biomedical diagnostics.

Key Features of OCI™-F

- Full VIS-NIR 400-1000 nm coverage
- Extremely compact and light-weighted
- Scanning with random speed, “true push-broom”
- Real-time image preview
- Innovative design significantly reduces system complexity and enhanced reliability
- Effortless system integration (e.g., less demanding on small UAV system)
- OCITM-F hyperspectral camera with a standard f=16 mm (24° FOV) lens, in an ultra-compact package

Table 2.2: Standard metadata for spectral library

Procedure	Metadata
i. Acquisition Date	Date of Acquisition
ii. Site Detail	Location
iii. Individual Selection	Sample name
iv. Spectral Reflectance	
a. Hyperspectral Camera Configuration	Field of View, Number of files
b. Observation Geometry	Solar and observation angle
c. Target Sample	Observation time, Sample type
v. Pre-Process	
a. Reflectance	Reference panel
b. Preparation	Number of spectra, algorithm applied
vi. Post Process	
a. Statistics	Number of files
b. Format save	File name, File Format
vii. Explosive Variability	Algorithm applied

Maps which are created using the remote sensing data are represented using a minimum mapping unit (MMU). An MMU is defined as “the smallest size areal entity to be mapped as a discrete entity”. For example, a derived classification of data using Landsat Enhanced Thematic Mapper plus (ETM+) data will typically have a nominal spatial resolution of 30 m (pixel size). A possible

MMU for a classification created from ETM+ data may be 8100 m or 90 90 m (3 3 pixels). The following are reasons why an MMU may be employed.

- a) There might be reduction in map accuracy if classification is performed at spatial resolution which is less than the MMU.
- b) The raw classified data will exhibit a “salt and pepper” effect as a result there may exist many single pixels from one particular class which might get interspersed with contiguous areas belonging to other classes. Also these data may get “smoothed” due the use of MMU.
- c) Problems related to geometric and positional error during conducting accuracy assessment of classification can be reduced by use of MMU.
- d) Spatial resolution of the reference data and classified map may not match.
- e) As the diffuse directional reflectance belonging to the neighbouring pixels can contribute to spectral signature of one given pixel as a result the individual pixel can be spectrally impure.

The above-mentioned points tell the importance of an appropriate MMU.

2.8 Existing Methods for Trace Detection of Explosives

A system in which operator or the sensor doesn't come in a direct physical contact with the explosives or the samples is referred to as standoff trace detection. This technology provides for a better capability for different architectures of security. There are several techniques for detecting traces of chemicals but some of the potential techniques are laser based spectroscopic techniques which include raman spectroscopy, laser induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), resonant raman spectroscopy, laser induced fluorescence (LIF), ion mobility spectrometry and hyperspectral remote sensing (P.M. Pellegrino et al., 2015, Edelman. G et al., 2012). The chemical sample prepared for the testing undergoes destruction during LIBS due to the uses the laser beam at a specific point. Due to its destructive nature the system consisting of LIBS is not recommended to be used on human and vehicles. Overall the system is having major drawback like it is more time consuming and the spatial coverage is less resulting in difficulty to scan large area in real conditions (J.L. Gottfried et al., 2008). Ion mobility spectrometry is another technique used frequently for trace detection but the system consisting of IMS have false alarm rate, matrix effects and the system distinguished between different chemicals based on physical molecular structure. (J.S. Caygill et al., 2012).LIF works on the principal of decomposing the molecules into characteristic fragments (C. Wynn et al., 2011, J. White et al.,2011). But LIF can detect only nitrogen containing explosive and require a laser source which can be tuned to different wavelength which result in thermal degradation of samples (C. Wynn et al., 2010). Many scientists and engineers from industry and academia have been working on implementing standoff trace detection method on different applications (D.S. Moore et al., 2004, S. Wallin et al., 2009, A.W. Fountain et al., 2014, M. Lopez-Lopez et al., 2014, P.M. Pellegrino et al., 2015, K.E. Brown et al., 2016, K.L. Gares et al., 2016, S. Elbasuney et al., 2016) but no technology has emerged as an optimum technique yet. Methods which are used today to scan suspicious objects on bomb site still have the operators at risk due to their close contact with the target (J. Yinon et al., 2007, M. Marshall et al., 2009, R.S. Golightly et al., 2009, N. Nuntawong et al., 2013, C. Martín-Alberca et al., 2014, Fernández de la et al., 2014, A.Hakonen et al., 2015,2016, P.R.Laska et al., 2016).

Therefore, a new technique is required in order to tackle the problem of detection of target objects by maintaining safety of the operator

Trace detection of chemical used in explosive involves several difficulties and challenges due to the physical properties of the traces. But some of the key challenges faced by the standoff off trace detection techniques are discussed below (Chaudhary S et al., 2019, Wen et al., 2018).

2.9 Challenges faced in standoff trace detection

Average area density (AAD) is defined as the total mass of the chemical in a given area. AAD calculated for the traces of the chemical (2gm) is very low as compared to the AAD of the background material (soil 20 gm). It can be visualized in conceptual Figure 2.9 (a) that small number of traces of chemicals is present on the surface of soil in a petri dish of 4cm diameter. AAD for traces of chemical is calculated to be 0.15 gm/cm^2 where as AAD for soil is 1.59 gm/cm^2

The traces of chemical cover very small area of the total area of the background. In the conceptual Figure 2.9 (b) it can be observed that traces occupy an area which is relatively very small as compared to the area of background. To overcome this problem the sensor should have high spatial resolution (small ground sampling distance) to identify the traces, while keeping the area coverage region high.

Due to environmental causes the traces of chemicals might be mixed with clutter materials which can be visualized at a microscopic scale in Figure 2.9 (b). This makes it very difficult to spatially sperate the received signals from the materials. A high level of clutter materials would tend to induce noise in the spectral reflectance of the chemical traces. This problem can be resolved by designing a refined algorithm having a strong discrimination capability based on the unique spectral response pf the chemicals.

Chemical (2 gm)

Soil (20 gm)

$$\text{Area} = 3.14 * 2^2 = 12.56 \text{ cm}^2$$

Figure 2.9(a): Conceptual example of traces of chemical present on the soil surface in a petri dish of 4cm diameter

Figure 2.9 (b): Conceptual example of a standoff trace detection sensor illustrating key challenges associated with standoff trace explosive chemical detection

Hence identification of explosives using standoff detection is a challenging task for researchers and engineers. Therefore, the main focus of defence research organization and forensic science is to develop a standoff trace detection technique which overcomes the key challenges discussed above and also carryout following requirements (Elbasuney and El-Sherif,2016):

- High selectivity
- Wide area coverage
- Potential to identify hidden explosive materials
- Minimize the risk of operators
- Non-destructive technique to avoid sample destruction
- Portable to crime scene

Images generated from HSI technique is also known as hypercube due to their three dimensions in which X, Y represent the spatial information of the image whereas Z gives information regarding the spectral property of the sample at different wavelength. It can also be viewed as a stack of two-dimensional images obtained at specific wavelength. The system collects a series of image planes which maps the intensity of reflected light from the surface at a given wavelength. Hyperspectral image is composed of a large number of pixels which gives the information regarding the reflection at a wavelength and is used to generate the spectral graph as shown in Figure 2. Use of HSI technique to perform standoff trace detection of explosives would be of great interest to the defence agencies across the globe as it would solve the problem of detection of target objects while maintain safety of the operators.

When chemical samples are exposed to a source of light with proper wavelength and energy, it results into an interaction of incident photons and the surface of chemical (Almeida et al., 2015; Lazic et al., 2011). The energy which is incident on the chemical sample can undergo several phenomena like absorption, transmission, scattering and reflection. The ratio of reflected energy to incident energy is termed as reflectance (Edelman et al., 2012). Information regarding the

chemical sample can be acquired by analyzing the amount of reflected energy which is a function of wavelength (Fernández de la Ossa et al.,2014). Chemical composition of the samples is a factor which determines the reflectivity and the signals reflecting from the surface of the chemical gets affected by the following parameters (Wen et al., 2018):

- Optical properties of the sample
- Illumination of light source
- Sensitivity of the detector

As discussed, reflectance is function of wavelength, therefore all chemicals used in explosives have their own unique spectral reflectance (El-Sharkawy and Elbasuney, 2017). An electronic database known as spectral library can be generated which can store reflectance of different explosive materials using their hypercube image. Since the hypercube image and spectral reflectance is unique for every explosive material it can be used for identifying and discriminating the various chemicals used in explosives (Serranti et al., 2018; Fang et al., 2018).

In most of the studies, Support Vector Machine (SVM) which is a machine learning technique was used for object classification (Colgan et al., 2012, Guyon et al., 2002, Hernault et al., 2010, Ma and Guo, 2014, Wang et al., 2011). It is an extensively used nonlinear classification technique. The algorithm tends to minimize the generalization errors by finding the optimum margin (hyperplane) between the support vectors to separate the classes. SVM has an advantage over other classification algorithms due to its performance with small sample, nonlinear and high dimensional dataset. This technique has been used for several applications, but not implemented for finding traces of chemicals in hyperspectral image.

2.10 Related works on trace detection of chemicals in other research fields using Hyperspectral Imaging System

Hyperspectral imaging techniques have been applied for detecting traces of chemicals in various fields like forensics, food science and agriculture. Sensors used in these studies for detecting the chemical have fine spatial resolution ranging from 0.3 mm to 14.2 mm and spectrum ranging from 300- 2500nm. The above-mentioned studies justify that trace detection of chemicals used in explosives can be implemented in near real time by using hyperspectral sensor with spatial resolution 0.12mm, spectrum ranging from 400-1000nm supported by artificial light sources. Classification techniques like SVM, CEM and dimensionality reduction techniques like PCA, EMD will be useful for making the system more accurate and faster.

Table 2.3: Application of Hyperspectral Imaging in various fields for determining traces of chemicals

Application	Technique	Particle Size	Spectrum Range	Spatial Resolution	Light Source	Real Time
Forensic Fingerprint Scanning	PLS-DA	5gm	1000-1700 nm	0.3 mm	Infra-red Lights	Yes

Explosive Detection	SVM	100ng	300-500 nm	0.58*3mm	Tungsten halogen lamps	Yes
Detecting Macronutrients	LS-SVM	-	380-1030 nm	14.2mm	Two 150W tungsten halogen lamps	No
Food Science	ICA	200 μ m Wheat flour	1000-2500 nm	0.42mm	150W tungsten halogen	No

2.11 Principal Component Analysis

It is used for transforming the information of hyperspectral data inherited in hundreds of narrow bands into new principal component images that contains more information and easier to interpret than original data. The dimensionality of data is reduced by compressing the data from high number of bands to few principal components. Generally, in hyperspectral data, the neighboring bands have mutual correlation or are inter correlated due to which there is repetition of information. If two variables A and B which are mutually correlated plotted using scatter diagram, it is observed a straight line defines their relationship. If these two variables are not perfectly correlated, then variability exists between two variables on some other axis. For representation the major axis is the dominating direction of variability while the second minor is drawn at right angle w.r.t major axis. Let X_1 and X_2 represent two bands in hyperspectral data and μ_1, μ_2 be the mean values of pixels for respective bands as shown in Figure 2.10. The distribution of pixels values in the scatter diagram represents the correlation between two bands and quality of information. If the pixel values are clustered it means very less information will be provided and original axis X_1 and X_2 are not good representation to analyze the information. Therefore, PCA is used to rotate or reproject the original axis to new axis (principal axis). New axis for the two bands X_1, X_2 are obtained first by translation: $X_1' = X_1 - \mu_1$; $X_2' = X_2 - \mu_2$

Once this translation is done the new coordinated is rotated by angle θ around the new origin. First axis X_1' is represented as principal component 1 because it has maximum amount of variance. Principal component 2 is perpendicular to PC1 and similarly PC3, PC4 can be calculated and arranged in order of decreasing variance.

Figure 2.10: Reprojection of original axis

2.12 Machine learning for Target Detection

Many definition of machine learning is available but a well-structured and posed definition is stated by Tom M. Mitchell “a computer program is said to learn from experience E with respect to some class of tasks T and performance measure P, if its performance at tasks in T, as measured by P, improves with experience E (Mitchell, 1997) and a simple example be predicting patterns of traffic in a crowded intersection (task T), if the data about traffic patterns in the past are available, one can learn it via a machine learning based algorithm (experience E) and, the algorithm has effectively learned, it will then be able to successfully predict the patterns of future traffic (performance measure P)”.

Different models are available for implementing machine learning for target detection, but the basic steps involved are shown in Figure 2.11:

Figure 2.11: Steps involved in machine learning

- I. Data Collection and Preparation: Raw data in format of excel, text or any other format is collected in this step which is also the foundation step for the whole process. Machine learning process becomes better if the volume of relevant data is high and dense. Further data needs to be cleaned by removing the missing values and removing the outliers.
- II. Training of the model: An appropriate model is selected and the cleaned dataset from the previous step is splitted into training and testing data. The training data is used to developing the model while test data is used for determing the accuracy of the model in the next step.
- III. Evaluating the model: Overall accuracy of the selected model is determined in this step by inputting a new dataset or test dataset
- IV. Refining the performance of model: To improve the performance of the model new variables are introduced or existing parameters are altered or new model is selcted.

Target detection algorithms can be classified into two categories namely, spectral matching algorithms and anomaly detection algorithms. Spectral matching algorithms is dependent upon the prior knowledge of the target spectra and the spectra obtained from the hyperspectral image is matched with the spectral library of the target. This knowledge base approach acts as limitation for this algorithm whereas these requirements are not needed in case of anomaly detection. Concept of image segmentation is utilized in anomaly detection in which the spectral response of every pixel is matched with the spectral response of the background, if the response is very different from the response of background the specific pixel is assigned as the target. Most of these algorithms require advance knowledge about the target to develop the model and this might be

difficult for military applications. Spectral matching algorithms can be implemented if spectral reflectance of desired target is available. These responses can be collected with help of spectrometers or pre existing spectral libraries can be used. Though, a large number of spectral matching algorithms have been reported in the literature, three algorithms namely Artificial Neural Network, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine (SVM) will be used in this study.

2.12.1 Artificial neural network (ANN)

ANN model is inspired by the neural structure of the brain and is based on the back-propagation algorithm (Nielsen, 2015). The structure of the model consists of nodes and connections which are arranged in three layers (input, hidden and output). The nodes present in the network contains the activation functions which are used to polarize and stabilize the network. By using the activation function a relationship is established between input variables and hidden nodes and similarly between hidden nodes and output variables. The hidden nodes learn and recognizes the pattern which is present in the input layer whereas the output layer which is the last layer of the network keeps a check on how the network is responding to the information learned (Krasnopolsky, 2007, Saha et al., 2002; Yesilnacar and Topal, 2005; Prasad et al., 2012). High number of hidden layers in the network tend to increase the processing time making the model more time consuming. Selection on number of hidden layers is based on trial and error basis. If the model created has less number of nodes then it will not be able to work on complex network, whereas if there is large number of nodes it will lead to over parameterization. The error in the model is minimized due to the back and forth learning approach. For a non-linear dataset ANN gives a satisfactory result but the training time is high when the nodes and connections develop a complex network. Conceptual architecture of ANN model is shown in Figure 2.12.

Sigmoidal relationship is assumed between the input variables and the activation rate of hidden nodes or between the hidden nodes and the activation rate of output nodes. Activation rate of hidden layer can be calculated using the equation below:

Figure 2.12: Architecture of ANN

$$\text{Logit (H1)} = W(\text{I1H1}) * \text{I1} + W(\text{I2H1}) * \text{I2} + W(\text{I3H1}) * \text{I3} + \text{Constant} = f$$

$$P(\text{H1}) = 1/(1+e^{(-f)})$$

Weights are recalibrated throughout the process which is an easy but lengthy process increasing the execution time. The error rates are only known at the output nodes. The weights on linkage between hidden and output nodes are recalibrated which is a function of error rate on output node.

$$\text{Error @ H1} = W(\text{H1O1}) * \text{Error@O1} + W(\text{H1O2}) * \text{Error@O2}$$

Weights for the links between the input and hidden nodes are recalibrated using the errors calculated in previous equation and this step is repeated continuously during the training of the model as shown in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13: Error computation in ANN

Figure 2.14: Weight calculation in ANN

2.12.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

SVM is a supervised machine learning technique which is derived from two theories (statistical and optimization), which helps the machine to implement classification with high accuracy and also avoid overfitting (Jakkula, 2006; Cristianini and Lkopf, 2002; Guo et al., 2005). SVM is popular among the machine learning algorithm due to its simple training process, better empirical performance on data with higher dimension and provides best trade-off between generalization and overfitting (Joachims, 1998; Brown et al., 2000; Cristianini and Lkopf, 2002; Huang et al., 2002). The main idea of SVM is to assign new samples into different classes. The architecture of SVM is shown in Figure 2.15. At first in the algorithm all the data items are plotted into n-dimensional space (one dimension each for one feature), this in turn represents the ordinate value of that coordinate for each values of the features. The model separates the classes by a surface called hyperplane such that the distance between the classes are maximum. Data points which are closest to the hyperplane are known as support vectors (Chapelle et al., 1999). Until the classes are well segregated or distinguished the process is repeated for a number of times or until some condition is satisfied. So what SVM does is that it maps all the data points in a space of high dimension and categorize the points using a kernel function.

Figure 2.15: Architecture of SVM

2.12.3 Random Forest

It is an ensemble-based machine learning supervised classification model which combines results from number of decision trees in a forest to determine the best class for the target pixel. The algorithms improve its performance by implementing the principle of divide and conquer. Ensemble methods work with the principle that a group of “weak learners” can come together to form a “strong learner”.

The algorithm takes place in two steps: (a) Creation of forest (b) Prediction class of target

The pseudocode for the implementation is presented herewith:

- **Creation**

- “k out of m features are randomly selected.
- From among k features, best split point is identified and the node d is calculated
- Recursively, nodes are splitted into daughter nodes.
- First three steps are repeated until the number of node is equal to l
- The process is repeated for n number of times to create forest with n trees

- **Prediction**

- Test feature is taken, and the decision tree rule created above is applied to predict the which is stored
- The process is repeated for several iteration (many decision trees) and the results are stored for each run

- Vote for each predicted target is calculated.
- Highest voted predicted target is considered as the final prediction from the random forest algorithm”

Figure 2.16: Architecture of Random Forest

2.13 Summary

For the trace detection of explosive purpose, a high spectral and spatial resolution is necessary for a good detection. Hyperspectral Imaging System (HSI) has the potential to carry out research with high selectivity, wide area coverage, capability to identify hidden explosive materials, minimize the risk of operators and without destruction to chemical samples. These potential characteristics of HSI has resulted it to emerge as a powerful tool which can be used for analysis of chemical traces. The traces can be identified and visualized by analysing the difference in the spectral reflectance of the trace and its background (Edelman. G et al., 2012). HSI is a high-speed data acquisition, non-invasive/destructive technique which is a combination of imaging and spectroscopy. This technique has been applied in various applications such as food engineering, agriculture, airborne survey, forensic science and mineralogy (Wei et al.,2014, Lelong et al., 1998, Giardino et al., 2015, Edelman. G et al., 2012, Fernández de la et al., 2014 Kruse et al., 2012). Therefore, it is a well-established technique for object detection, monitoring the quality of the surface and studying the composition of the sample. HSI is a suitable technique for trace detection of residue of explosives due to its notable combination of imaging and spectroscopy, capability to determine the composition of each pixel generated in the cubic image within a fast response time (Smekens and Gouhier, 2018) which makes it more advantageous over the current spectroscopy methods which only provide spectral information ignoring spatial information about the traces of explosives. Individual spectra generated from HSI gives rich spectral and spatial information which works as a powerful tool for quantification and identification of the samples in a more efficient manner. The HSI system is undergoing rapid development making the system more

portable with high area coverage so that it can be used at the crime scene to view and interpret the samples in real time. The development of such techniques will help in making new semi-automated explosive detection systems that will have higher probability of detection and lower false alarm rate.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overall Methodology

In this study, the explosive chemicals like TNT, C4, AN are considered and were provided by the foundation Innovation for Happiness. The whole study can be divided into three stages. In the first stage of research the sample were collected and prepared according to the experiments. After the preparation of the chemical samples, setting up of the light sources and hyperspectral imaging system. Hyperspectral sensor was used to acquire the raw images of the sample in the spectrum of 400-1000 nm using Spec Grabber. Cube creator and ENVI software were used to create the hyperspectral cube, selection of region of interest and to generate the spectral response of different chemicals in the indoor lightning conditions. The spectral response of the chemicals were processed and stored as spectral library which were used for trace detection in the outdoor field. PCA and first derivative were applied on the spectral response using R Studio to determine the important wavelengths to reduce the dimensionality of the hyperspectral data. In the second stage of the study SVM, ANN and RF classification model were developed on training and testing datasets for determining the traces of the chemicals with soil samples as background. The models were developed using all 144 bands and with the optimal wavelengths selected from dimensionality reduction technique i.e 22 bands. Accuracy assessment of all the models were performed using the confusion matrix, kappa coefficient and balanced accuracy. In the end of the second stage a comparative study was done between the three-classification model for the purpose of trace detection.

The third stage of the study focuses on determining the altitude and speed of the sensor and minimum size of the chemical that can be detected with an acceptable accuracy. To determine the suggested altitude the images were acquired at different altitude varying from 40cm to 150 cm and accuracy assessment was done using the model developed in the second stage of the study. Similarly, minimum size of the chemical was determined to know the detection limit of the sensor at a suggested altitude. Size of the samples in the experiment were varied from 0.25 cm to 1 cm. Figure 3.1 illustrates a general block diagram of this process.

*1: SpecGrabber , *2: CubeCreator , *3: ENVI , *4: R Studio

Figure 3.1: Overall methodology

3.2 Software and Hardware Requirements

Hardware requirements for the research were hyperspectral sensor with 144 spectral bands with wavelength ranging from 400-1000nm, minicomputer with operating system as windows 7, processor Intel core i5 or advanced, solid state storage device and minimum 8GB RAM dedicated only for acquiring raw images and processing it to cube files. Light source for different wavelengths like ultraviolet, visible and infrared region were required to provide uniform distribution of light. Conveyor belt along with motor was required to attach the hyperspectral sensor to perform the pushbroom scanning. The chemicals required in the study were TNT, C₄ and ammonium nitrate which were placed in the black petri dishes.

Hyperspectral images were generated by data processing using Cube Creator which is product of Bayspec. The hyperspectral images created were further processed and analysed in ENVI and R for creation of spectral library and doing the analysis.

Table 3.1 Software Requirements

S.No.	Software	Application
1	SpecGrabber	Controlling camera parameters and Acquiring raw images
2	Cube Creator	Mosaicking and Creating hyperspectral cube
3	ENVI	Image processing, developing spectral library
4	R	Machine learning, Statistical Analysis

Table 3.2: Lab Requirements

S.No.	Chemical/Material	Specification
1	TNT, C4, Ammonium Nitrate	0.044 mol, 0.045 mol, 0.124 mol respectively
2	Black Petri dishes	
3	Tungsten Halogen Lamp	150W, 420 - 900 nm
4	Infrared Lamp	150W, 600 – 950 nm
5	Motor and Conveyor Belt	Speed 1cm/sec
6	Hyperspectral Sensor	144 bands, 400 – 1000nm
7	Spectroradiometer	
8	Sample Platform	30 cm in length

In the chapter development of spectral library for chemicals used in explosives the experiments were performed on the chemicals like TNT, C4 and AN inside the laboratory using artificial light sources like halogen and infrared lamp. The expected outcome from these experiments were to store the spectral response of all the chemicals in the spectrum of 400-1000 nm which can be used for real field applications. The spectral library generated from this chapter was used to train the model developed using SVM, ANN and RF in the chapter supervised trace detection of explosives using machine learning algorithm. The developed model was used for determining traces of chemicals present in the hyperspectral image collected from field.

CHAPTER 4

DEVELOPMENT OF SPECTRAL LIBRARY FOR CHEMICALS USED IN EXPLOSIVES

4.1 Introduction

Due to continuous increase in terrorist activities throughout the world, security measures have increased and there is demand for developing new techniques which can detect explosives. Security departments believe that first response of security threat comes in the form of suspect packages or chemical powders while scanning the cargos or containers at airport and seaports (Klunder, Nguyen & Margalith, 2011). Several instruments are available for detection of explosives, but the most common technique used at airport is IMS. The technique is fast and reliable, but it is not a standoff trace detection technique, membrane or a filter is used to swipe the baggage which thermally absorbs the residue in IMS.

In this chapter we discuss spectral responses of different chemicals used in explosives collected using hyperspectral sensor and development of spectral library. Later we develop a system which is capable of finding traces of chemicals in the acquired hyperspectral image using the spectral library developed. Initial scope of the chapter is to study the spectrum of different light sources and collect the spectral response of chemicals under different light sources.

Spectral imaging system records the spectral reflectance and spatial information. A set of images are recorded at different wavelengths due to which a spectral cube is generated. Each pixel in the spectral cube represents the spectrum of the scene at that point. Spectral imaging is categorized into hyperspectral and multispectral based on the spectral resolution. The spectral and spatial information can be represented and displayed on spectral maps comprehensively by deriving two-dimensional spectral information from a series or set of complete images which is one of the major advantages, on spectral maps different artificial colors are annotated to pixel clusters which belong to different classes. (Balas, Epitropou, Tsapras & Hadjinicolaou, 2018). Spectra collected using Raman spectroscopy shows peaks and valleys which are related to the atomic structure of the target (Mosca et al., 2016). But the cost of such equipment is high and optical lenses for Mid IR spectroscopy are not available in many cases for commercial purposes.

Hyperspectral sensor measures the reflection of light by molecules in the wavelength range from 400-1000 nm. The predominant reflection features are due to the CH, OH, NH vibrational overtones and combination bands (Klunder, Nguyen & Margalith, 2011). Since many energetic materials contain these groups, they will have unique spectra in the VSNIR and thus, it should be capable of identifying many explosives.

In this chapter we present:

- Study of different light sources
- Comparison of hyperspectral sensor and spectrometer
- Presenting and setting up hyperspectral imaging system which utilizes a halogen and infrared light source to illuminate the samples
- Studying spectral response of different chemicals under halogen and infrared light source
- Development of spectral library for different chemicals used in explosives

4.2 Methodology

To achieve first objective the experiments were conducted initially on non-explosive chemicals like NaCl, NaNO₃ and KNO₃ and later it was implemented on explosives like TNT, C4 and ANFO. Non-explosive chemicals were used to study the effect of different light conditions and completion of laboratory setup. Sample preparation, method for laboratory setup, experiments to study light conditions and methodology for developing spectral library for non-explosives chemical are discussed below. For creation of spectral library for different quantities of available explosives like TNT, C4 and ANFO using hyperspectral sensor following methodology and experiments were implemented as shown in Figure 4.1 below.

Figure 4.1: Flow of Methodology for Objective 1

4.2.1 Sample Preparation

In this study, composition C4 which is a plastic explosive with a texture like clay, ammonium nitrate and 2,4,6-trinitrotoluene (TNT) were used. C4 is a dirty white, light brown solid and it smells like motor oil whereas TNT is a yellow solid. Composition of C4 varies according to the manufacturers but 90% is research department explosive (RDX) and remaining 10% is a mixture of polyisobutylene, dioctyl sebacate and mineral oil (Meyer et al., 2016, Mahoney et al., 2010). C4 is considered resistant to physical shocks and it can explode only when the detonator inside the explosive is exposed to fire. The chemical can be molded easily into different shapes to vary the direction of explosion. A total of 20 samples of pure chemical AN (10 gm), C4 (10 gm) and TNT (10 gm) and 10 samples of soil (20 gm) mixed with AN (2 gm), C4 (5 gm) and TNT (2 gm) were used in this study. Chemical samples were prepared after weighing them accurately. The weighted chemical samples were placed in petri dishes with a black body and a diameter of 4 cm. Average areal density of AN, TNT was 0.16 gm/cm^2 whereas for C4 and soil it was calculated to be 0.39 gm/cm^2 , 1.59 gm/cm^2 respectively. Samples were mixed, distributed and levelled uniformly in the petri dishes to reduce surface roughness. Petri dishes were placed over a black platform to minimize any reflection from the background.

4.2.2 Setup of Hyperspectral Imaging System

Hyperspectral imaging system was assembled at a laboratory scale to obtain hyperspectral images of the chemical samples based on reflectance. The reflectance data in the laboratory was obtained by BaySpec OCI F hyperspectral sensor which consists of a charge couple device which has a readout mode, specifications of the hyperspectral sensor is shown in Table 4.1. The images were acquired by pushbroom scanning in 144 bands with spectral resolution of 4.16 nm from 400-1000 nm using software SpecGrabber (Super Gamut, BaySpec, Inc.). Measurements were taken using 150W halogen and 150W infrared lamps as the light sources positioned 90 cm from the sample at an angle of 45° to the zenith as shown in Figure 4.2 (Zhang et al., 2016, Shao et al., 2018). Intensity of the halogen lamp used in the experiment decreases after 700 nm, therefore infrared lamp is used along with halogen lamp to have uniform intensity throughout the spectrum of 400-1000 nm. For acquisition of spectral data, the sensor was placed 40cm above the stage on which the chemical samples were placed. To complete the scanning of the chemical samples in one single scan line, the sensor was attached to a conveyor belt which moved at a speed of 1cm/s. Hyperspectral sensor placed at the nadir detected the reflected energy in the area of $15.4\text{cm} * 12.3 \text{ cm}$ (Figure 4.3) with a field of view of 22° (Figure 4.4) at 144 bands as shown in Figure 4.5. Spatial resolution (pixel/mm) is a function of distance between the sample and the sensor at nadir position, for laboratory condition it was calculated to be 0.012 cm. The samples prepared were placed in black petri dishes of diameter 4 cm and they were placed over a black platform to minimize any sort of reflection from background. The samples inside the petri dishes were levelled uniformly to reduce surface roughness.

Figure 4.2(a): Pure chemicals AN, TNT & C4

Figure 4.2(b): Laboratory Setup

Table 4.1 Sensor Details

Scanning Technique	Push Broom
Field of View (FOV)	22°
Focal Length	16mm
Frame Per Second	45 fps
Swath	15.4 cm*12.3 cm
Spatial Resolution	0.012 cm
Spectral Bands	144
Spectral Resolution	4.16 nm (FWHM)
Height of Sensor	40 cm

Figure 4.3: Field of View

Figure 4.4: Scanning Angle

Figure 4.5: Pushbroom Scanning

4.2.3 Data Processing of Hyperspectral Image

Hyperspectral image calibration, selection of region of interest and extraction of spectral data. The white reference image was acquired using a circular white surface of teflon (8cm diameter). This image was used for calibration of the sensor and it behaved like a perfect Lambertian surface and in the spectral range of 400-1000 nm it achieved minimum 95% reflection value. Whereas, dark reference image acquired by covering the camera lens with its cover and keeping all the light sources off Spectral reflectance data (R) was calculated by calibrating the maximum raw intensity (I) to ideal white intensity (I_w) and black background (I_b).

$$R = (I - I_b)/(I_w - I_b) \quad \text{Equation 4.1}$$

where I is intensity of the raw image, I_w is the intensity of the white reference image and I_b is the intensity of the dark reference image. CubeCreator software (Super Gamut, BaySpec, Inc.) was used to apply corrections in the hyperspectral image.

The acquired hyperspectral image is a rectangular image which needs to be cropped so that analysis is performed on the sample of interest. To perform cropping on the image, region of interest (ROI) needs to be predefined to extract the spectral information. In this study, the ROI for each chemical sample in the hyperspectral image was defined manually and spectral information for the ROI was extracted (Vidal et al., 2012). Final spectrum to represent the chemical sample was calculated by averaging the spectrum of all pixels within the ROI. This further resulted in the creation of spectral library by putting the average spectrum of each samples together in one file. Calibration, selection of the region of interest, and the extraction of the spectral data were performed in ENVI (Environment for Visualization of Images; ITT Visual Solutions) and R studio.

To study effect of artificial light sources like halogen lamp and infra-red lamp on the spectral reflectance. Two artificial light sources one halogen lamp of 150 W and one IR lamp of 150 W was placed in opposite direction at angle of 45° covering the spectrum from 400-1000nm. Spectrum of halogen, infrared and combination of both were determined by recording the reflectance of white reflector using the spectrometer. The light sources were arranged in such a way that light intensity was uniformly distributed around FOV. Light intensity was measured in Lux using a luxmeter at 13 different points in the field of view. The flow of the work is shown in

Figure 4.6. To study the reliability of hyperspectral sensor by comparing the spectral reflectance of samples using spectroradiometer and hyperspectral sensor. Spectral reflectance for samples like vegetation, soil and concrete were determined using both handheld spectroradiometer and hyperspectral sensor as shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.6: Methodology for Collecting Light Intensity

Figure 4.7: Methodology for Validation of Hyperspectral Sensor

Spectral data of all the three chemicals were collected using hyperspectral camera. A total of 30 samples of pure chemical were used in this study which includes 10 samples each of TNT, C4 and AN 0.044 mol, 0.045 mol, 0.124 mol respectively as explained in Figure 4.8. All the samples were collected by Foundation Innovation for Happiness. Hyperspectral camera was moved in X axis direction by using motor to perform pushbroom scanning of the samples placed on the platform. The hyperspectral camera acquires data with a nadir view from a height of 40 cm in 144 narrow contiguous spectral bands with bandwidth of 4.16 nm. All the spectral measurements were acquired in same light conditions to avoid the impact of illumination changes on the spectral responses. Spectral responses collected were converted into spectral reflectance using the readings of white reflectance panel and dark reference. Hyperspectral cube of the samples was prepared using CubeCreator software, then the raw spectrum was generated using ENVI for further analyses. Spectra for individual chemical samples were plotted using z profile in ENVI and it was ensured that no outliers were included for further analysis.

The developed spectral library consists of mean reference spectra of the chemicals and is built using the spectral module in ENVI software. The naming (labelling) of each spectrum of the spectral library has been done in such a way that the name of the spectrum indicates name of the chemical, its source (indicator of site of sample collected).

Figure 4.8: Developing spectral library

4.3 Result and Discussions

4.3.1 Selection of light source

Spectrum of different light sources like halogen and infrared lamp and combination of halogen, infrared were studied to select the light source which covers the spectrum of 400-1000 nm with more than 95% reflectance on Teflon. Halogen lamp covered the spectrum of 400-700nm and infrared lamp covered the spectrum of 650-1000 nm. While performing the experiments the light sources were placed at distance of 90 cm and uniform distribution of light intensity throughout the FOV was maintained. Luxmeter was used to measure the intensity at 13 different positions in the FOV with having an average of 205 lux. The initial experiment was performed by keeping the sensor at an altitude of 40cm due to the constraint of the HSI to collect the spectral response of the chemicals. Before collecting the spectral response calibration of the sensor was performed using white and dark reflectance surfaces. Since the whole system was calibrated it was observed that even on increasing the height of the sensor the response remained the same in future experiments as conducted in chapter 6. It was observed that the combination of halogen and infrared lamp covered the whole spectrum with a uniform spectral reflectance greater than 95% as shown in Figure 4.9. Spectral reflectance for a chemical was calculated for different light conditions and it was observed that spectral reflectance varied by changing the light sources. To know the appropriate light source for the research similarity matrix was generated using pearson correlation for halogen, infrared and combination of both as shown in Table 4.2. When halogen and infrared lamp was used together it showed a correlation of 0.94 and 0.98 with the results of infrared and halogen lamp respectively.

Figure 4.9: Spectrum of Halogen and Infrared Lamp working together

Table 4.2: Similarity matrix for different light sources

	Similarity Matrix		
	Combination	IR	Halogen
Combination	1.00	.83	.96
IR	.83	1.00	.71
Halogen	.96	.71	1.00

Another experiment was performed to study the distribution of light intensity in the field of view of the sensor. The aim of the experiment was to determine the correct position of the light sources where it should be placed so that throughout the future experiments a uniform light distribution can be observed in the field of view of the camera without any shadow. Light intensity in the FOV was determined and the plot of the light intensity is shown in Figure 4.10.

Figure 4.10: Distribution of Light Intensity in the FOV

4.3.2 Spectral reflectance profile

Mean spectral reflectance of 20 chemical samples of AN, C4 and TNT along with soil and vegetation in the spectral range 400-1000 nm is illustrated in Figure 4.11. Spectral reflectance of the chemicals AN, C4 and TNT behave differently from soil and vegetation in the spectral range of 400-1000 nm which makes it easy to distinguish between explosives and non-explosives (soil and vegetation). In order to find the type of explosive used, spectral reflectance of all the three chemicals need to be analysed. Samples of C4 and TNT showed similar trend of spectral reflectance from 400 nm till around 540 nm. From 580 nm onwards, reflectance of C4 gradually increases as compared to TNT and AN. After 572 nm there is a sharp drop in spectral reflectance of TNT, small drop for AN and it forms a valley in between 597 nm and 625nm and remains almost constant with small change in reflectance value till 970 nm. As shown in Figure 4.10, chemical C4 can be differentiated from TNT and AN in the spectrum window of 580 - 1000 nm. Similarly, AN and TNT can be differentiated as spectral reflectance of AN is always higher than TNT.

Figure 4.11: Spectral reflectance of AN, C4 and TNT

4.4 Chapter Summary

In this chapter spectral reflectance library for the TNT, C4 and AN used in the explosives was developed using the hyperspectral imaging system. To achieve this objective several experiments were performed in the laboratory conditions. The chemicals used in the study were provided by the foundation Innovation for Happiness. The hyperspectral imaging system consisted of hyperspectral sensor, conveyor belt and external light sources. Dark room with a controlled

environment was created to perform the experiment and to study the spectral responses of different light sources. In this study halogen and infrared lamp were selected as the external light sources. BaySpec hyperspectral camera with a field of view of 22°, spectral range of 400-1000 nm, spatial resolution of 0.012 cm at 40cm altitude and spectral resolution of 4.16nm was used to acquire raw images of the chemical samples. Softwares like CubeCreator and ENVI were used to create hyperspectral cube, selection of ROI and for generation of spectrum. The developed spectral reflectance library will be used as an input to the machine learning algorithm in the next chapter to identify traces of chemicals in the image. In the next chapter PCA and first derivative would be applied on the spectral reflectance library to determine the optimal wavelengths and library would be used for supervised trace detection.

CHAPTER 5

SUPERVISED TRACE DETECTION OF EXPLOSIVES USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

5.1 Introduction

Trace detection of chemicals on soil can be achieved using several machine learning algorithms. Detection of chemicals can be grouped as spectral matching algorithms and anomaly detection algorithms. Spectral matching algorithms use the pre-acquired spectral responses of different chemicals to find the traces of chemicals. These spectral responses are collected from the hyperspectral images of pure chemical samples which are stored in database as spectral library. This knowledge base approach acts as limitation for this algorithm whereas anomaly detection algorithms do not have any such requirement.

On other hand anomaly detection algorithms works on the approach of image segmentation. The algorithm doesn't require prior knowledge about spectral response of chemical of interest. Each pixel's spectral response is compared with respect to local background which is a part of image or global background which is the whole image, if the pixel's spectral response varies randomly or in an abrupt manner then the pixel can be further considered to be a part of target object pixel. For military applications it is difficult to acquire spectral response for target of interest which are used for spectral modelling.

Though, a large number of spectral matching algorithms have been reported in the literature, three algorithms namely Artificial Neural Network, Random Forest and Support Vector Machine (SVM) will be used in this study. These algorithms are implemented using the spectral library developed for chemicals used in explosives using hyperspectral spectral sensor in previous chapter. ANN and SVM are used to identify the pixels which matches with the spectral responses of reference spectrum.

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 Dimensionality Reduction and Optimal Wavelength Selection

HSI generates a large amount of high dimensional data which is complex and redundant, making it difficult to analyze without the support of multivariate analytical methods (Silva et al., 2017). Principal component analysis (PCA) is a well-established statistical method (Cavaignac et al., 2017; Gosselin et al., 2011) and an efficient technique to be applied on the hyperspectral cube to decompose the highly correlated spectral data and reduce their dimensionality. New variables called principal components (PC) are formed which are not correlated to each other and are linear combination of the original variables (Xing et al., 2007). Original information with minimal loss can be represented by combination of few principal components. To reduce computational time and cost of analysis, dimensionality of the image should be reduced which can be achieved by choosing the most significant wavelengths from the spectral region where the spectral pattern differs the most (Osborne, Künnemeyer, Osborne & Jordan, 1997). PCA analysis and first derivative was applied on the hyperspectral image data to select the important wavelength. The PC generated from PCA are used to analyze the common features between the samples because

samples which have similar spectral reflectance tend to cluster in the score plot of principal components (Hu et al., 2017). Loading matrix resulting from PCA indicates the contribution of each wavelength in the PC which helps in selecting the wavelengths which are most effective in discriminating different chemical samples.

Figure 5.1: Selection of important wavelength

Hyperspectral image in BSQ format was imported in ENVI and using the clip tool four different raster image was generated for all different chemicals. These new raster images was imported in R using package raster and RSToolbox. After converting the raster image into dataframe format principal component analysis was applied on it to calculate the variance of every principal component and loadings for individual principal component to determine the wavelengths contributing maximum to the principal component.

5.2.2 Supervised Classification

After acquisition of hyperspectral image, the reflectance values of samples of chemical and soil were imported into R dataframe and split randomly into a training and testing dataset with the ratio of 70:30; which were both used to establish the classification model. Various supervised classification techniques such as ANN, RF, SVM are considered for classification of multispectral and hyperspectral remote sensing data. To detect traces of chemicals accurately, classification model was built using the spectral reflectance data of chemicals. In this study, SVM and ANN were used over other classification models for identifying the traces of chemicals in the hyperspectral image. SVM was used because of its simple architecture, better performance with low number of inputs to the model, less prone to overfitting and requirement of less time and memory to store predictive model (Bousquet and Elisseff et al., 2002; Devos et al., 2009; Langeron et al., 2007; Li et al., 2014). Two SVM models were established in this study, the first model used all the 144 wavelengths in the spectral range of 400-1,000 nm as the input whereas the second model was based on optimal wavelengths selected.

SVM algorithm determined an optimal surface called hyperplane which separates the classes from each other (Wang et al., 2011). The algorithm selects the most suitable hyperplane on the basis of maximum margin between each class. SVM is a suitable technique to work efficiently with both

linear and nonlinear data with good generalization ability. For classification of spectral data SVM had been proved as a reliable and efficient method. In this study SVM was performed on R studio by defining the kernel functions and by determining the parameters.

The kernel function used here was radial basis function (RBF) which can explicit the relation between the target variable and independent variable, and grid search procedure along with 10-fold cross validation were used to optimize the parameters of SVM. Classification accuracy is used to assess the performances of SVM models.

ANN model is inspired by the neural structure of the brain and is based on the back-propagation algorithm (Nielsen, 2015). The structure of the model consists of nodes and connections which are arranged in three layers (input, hidden and output). The nodes present in the network contains the activation functions which are used to polarize and stabilize the network. By using the activation function a relationship is established between input variables and hidden nodes and similarly between hidden nodes and output variables. The hidden nodes learn and recognizes the pattern which is present in the input layer whereas the output layer which is the last layer of the network keeps a check on how the network is responding to the information learned (Krasnopolsky, 2007, Saha et al., 2002; Yesilnacar and Topal, 2005; Prasad et al., 2012). High number of hidden layers in the network tend to increase the processing time making the model more time consuming. Selection on number of hidden layers is based on trial and error basis. If the model created has less number of nodes then it will not be able to work on complex network, whereas if there is large number of nodes it will lead to over parameterization. The neural network was performed using 'nnet' package in R language. The error in the model is minimized due to the back and forth learning approach. For a non-linear dataset ANN gives a satisfactory result but the training time is high when the nodes and connections develop a complex network.

Figure 5.2 Architecture of ANN Model

Figure 5.3 Different activation functions in ANN Model

Figure 5.4 Methodology for Objective 2

Figure 5.5: Methodology for developing classification model

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Principal component analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied on the hyperspectral image acquired by the imaging system to perform dimensionality reduction by obtaining major principal components (PC). To construct a PCA model for possible 60,000 spectra of each sample was computationally expensive. Therefore, to reduce the computation load, a random sample of 40,000 spectra for each sample was selected for construction of PCA model. No significant change in the PC was observed when the number of random points were increased. PCA was performed over 144 bands and 10 PC were generated, first four PC are listed in Table 5.1 for spectrum profile between 400-1000 nm. PC1, PC2 and PC3 explained variance of 87.97 %, 0.53 % and 0.39 %, respectively. First 10 PC explained cumulative variance of 90.9 % of the raw information as shown in Figure 6.

Table 5.1. Variance of individual principal components

Principal Component	Variance
PC1	87.97
PC2	0.53
PC3	0.39
PC4	0.30

Figure 5.6: Cumulative variance of first ten principal components

5.3.2 Optimal Wavelength Selection

Sine HSI generates a large amount of high dimensional data which is complex and redundant, making it difficult to analyze without the support of multivariate analytical methods (Silva et al., 2017). Aim of optimal wavelength selection is to select only those wavelengths from a set of 144 wavelengths which carry the most important information after decomposing the highly correlated spectral data and reduce their dimensionality. In this study, loading values from PCA and first derivative of spectra were used to select the optimal wavelengths. As discussed in the previous

section, hyperspectral image consists of large amounts of data and it also suffers from the curse of dimensionality. In this study, the dimensionality of the image was 144 and operation on all 144 bands would decrease the system performance. The spectra of the image obtained had high correlation with the neighbouring bands resulting in a complex model (Nubiato et al., 2018). To solve the problem of high dimensionality of the image it was important to select the wavelengths which carry most valuable information, so that analysis could be performed on these selected wavelengths later to improve the performance. In Table 5.1 and Figure 5.6, it was shown that variance of PC1, PC2 and PC3 explained variance of 87.97, 0.53 and 0.39 respectively and cumulative variance of first ten principal components is 90.9. To select the optimal wavelengths, loading plots of first 3 PC were analyzed. Peaks and valleys in the loading plot of PC1 and PC3 as shown in Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8, which explain that high absolute (abs) loading values, were selected as optimal wavelengths for identifying the chemicals effectively (Zhang et al., 2016, Shao et al., 2018). First derivative method processed the spectral reflectance of the chemical to find the wavelengths where the value of first derivative becomes zero, these wavelengths were selected as optimal wavelengths as shown in Figure 5.9 (García et al., 2007). 22 optimal wavelengths were selected in the spectral range of 400-1000 nm using the first three PC and first derivative and they are listed in the Table 5.2.

Figure 5.7: Absolute loadings for first principal component

Figure 5.8: Absolute loadings for third principal components

Figure 5.9: First derivative of spectra

Table 5.2: Selected optimal wavelength

Spectral Range (nm)	Optimal Wavelengths Selected (nm) (combining Loading and First derivative)	Number of wavelengths
400-600	426,451,467,479,508,520,536,556	8
600-800	665,693,717,729,733,761,765	7
800-1,000	805,829,845,853,865,925,961	7

5.3.3 SVM classification model

The spectral library generated from hyperspectral image data was used to develop a SVM model that can be used for identifying traces of chemical and type of chemical present more accurately. SVM model was built using caret package in R studio on the training dataset and tested on the testing dataset to check the accuracy. For developing the SVM model A, the 144 spectral sample datasets were split into training and testing dataset with the ratio of 70:30. After splitting, 4200 spectral observations were made in the training dataset whereas 1800 observations were made in the testing data. The accuracy of the model was measured using overall accuracy and kappa coefficient. Number of correctly classified classes from all classes is termed as overall accuracy whereas kappa coefficient is an effective way of measuring performance of the model as it can be used for multiclass and imbalanced classes. In the spectral range of 400-1,000 nm, the SVM model A achieved a discrimination accuracy and kappa coefficient of 86.48%, 81.97% for the training dataset and 81.11%, 74.81% for testing dataset. SVM model B was developed using the 22 optimal wavelengths in Table 3 and it achieved the discrimination accuracy, kappa coefficient of 86.71%, 74.81 in training dataset and 77.17%, 69.59 in testing dataset. An accuracy assessment for both SVM models are shown in Figure 5.10 and class wise classification results and confusion matrix for model established on 144 wavelengths (SVM model A) and on 22 selected wavelengths (SVM model B) are shown in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively. With the pixel size of 0.012cm, the traces of AN, C4 and TNT were identified successfully while some pixels of soil, C4 and TNT were misclassified. Misclassification might have occurred because the difference of the spectral reflectance at certain wavelengths were not significant.

Figure 5.10: Accuracy assessment of SVM model on full spectra (SVM Model A) and SVM model on optimal wavelength (SVM Model B)

Trade-off between cost and accuracy of the SVM model using radial function was determined by varying the cost from 0.25 to 128 and it was observed that the accuracy increased from 0.72 to 0.864 respectively. Tuning parameter sigma was held constant at a value of 4.86. Accuracy was used to select the optimal model using the largest value. The final values used for the model were sigma = 0.006 and C = 4.

Classification results of the SVM model using full spectra and optimal wavelength for identifying AN, C4, TNT and soil were satisfactory as all the four classes achieved an accuracy of more than 76% in the training and 70% in the testing dataset. Whereas execution time of SVM model B based on optimal wavelengths was reduced to almost half than the model A based on full spectra. For all individual classes: C4, AN, TNT and soil, class accuracy was calculated to measure the performance of the classification based on the confusion matrix. There were 241, 173, 150 and 4 pixels which were misclassified during training of SVM model A gave an accuracy of 76.71%, 83.25%, 86.12% and 99.61%. During testing of SVM model A 131, 89, 98 and 22 pixels were misclassified, achieved an accuracy of 70.36%, 79.59%, 79.19% and 95.12%. Similarly, individual

classes in the SVM model B gave an accuracy of 76.47%, 84.32%, 86.30% and 99.71% during training and 70.51%, 73.85%, 77.38% and 95.90% during testing.

Table 5.3: Classification results of SVM model A

Prediction \ Reference	SVM Model A Training				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy (%)
C4	794	150	91	0	76.71
AN	145	860	28	0	83.25
TNT	107	40	931	3	86.12
Soil	4	0	0	1047	99.61
SVM Model A Testing					
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy (%)
C4	311	75	51	5	70.36
AN	79	347	10	0	79.59
TNT	56	26	373	16	79.19
Soil	4	2	16	429	95.12

Table 5.4: Classification results of SVM model B on optimal wavelengths

Prediction \ Reference	SVM Model B Training				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy (%)
C4	806	170	77	1	76.47
AN	135	839	21	0	84.32
TNT	107	41	951	3	86.30
Soil	2	0	1	1046	99.71
SVM Model B Testing					
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy (%)
C4	318	80	53	0	70.51
AN	94	305	14	0	73.85
TNT	70	31	366	6	77.38
Soil	12	0	7	444	95.90

5.3.5 RF classification model

Classification results of the RF model A using full spectra and optimal wavelength for identifying AN, C4, TNT and soil were satisfactory as all the four classes achieved an accuracy of more than 76% in the training and 69% in the testing dataset. Whereas execution time of RF model B based on optimal wavelengths was reduced to more than half than the model A based on full spectra. For all individual classes: C4, AN, TNT and soil, class accuracy was calculated to measure the performance of the classification based on the confusion matrix. There were 182, 238, 143 and 4 pixels which were misclassified during training of SVM model A gave an accuracy of 76.21%,

78.30%, 86.45% and 99.64%. During testing of RF model A 128, 92, 122 and 14 pixels were misclassified, achieved an accuracy of 69.88%, 76.88%, 75.89% and 97.03%. Similarly, individual classes in the RF model B gave an accuracy of 76.32%, 79.37%, 80.21% and 97.92% during training and 73.57%, 75.58%, 77.66% and 92.13% during testing.

Table 5.5 (a): Confusion Matrix of RF model A

Reference Prediction	RF Model A (Training)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	583	134	46	2	76.21
AN	187	859	51	0	78.30
TNT	104	31	912	8	86.45
Soil	0	4	0	1104	99.64
Reference Prediction	RF Model A (Testing)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	297	98	27	3	69.88
AN	81	306	11	0	76.88
TNT	67	12	384	43	75.89
Soil	0	2	12	457	97.03

Table 5.5 (b): Confusion Matrix of RF model B

Reference Prediction	RF Model B (Training)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	564	151	22	2	76.32
AN	158	827	57	0	79.37
TNT	183	19	904	0	80.21
Soil	0	7	15	1035	97.92
Reference Prediction	RF Model B (Testing)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	245	67	15	6	73.57
AN	78	294	17	0	75.58
TNT	52	12	358	39	77.66
Soil	0	6	31	433	92.13

5.3.5 ANN classification model

The spectral library generated from hyperspectral image data was used to develop a ANN model that can be used for identifying traces of chemical and type of chemical present more accurately. ANN model was built using nnet package in R studio on the training dataset and tested on the testing dataset to check the accuracy. For developing the ANN model A, the spectral sample dataset was split into training and testing dataset with the ratio of 70:30. After splitting, 4200 spectral observations were made in the training dataset whereas 1800 observations were made in the testing data. In this study two ANN models were established, first model (A) was established using all 144 spectral bands and model (B) was established using 22 optimal selected bands using PCA. Model A produced a satisfactory result with an accuracy of 92.31% but the execution or run time was high making the process costly. Both the models were established using 3 hidden layers on the basis on mean square error (MSE). MSE produced by 3 hidden layers were less than MSE produced by other combination of hidden layers. For the calibration dataset the accuracy, RMSE and kappa for model A was 92.31%, 0.34 and 0.89 whereas for validation dataset it was 71%, 0.43 and 0.64 as shown in Figure 5.11. The use of 22 PCA selected optimum bands along with 3 hidden layers produced satisfactory results with accuracy, RMSE, kappa coefficient of 72%, 0.75, 0.64 and reduced the execution time by six times making it more efficient. In Model B redundant data and outlier were removed.

Table 5.6: Confusion Matrix of ANN model A

Reference Prediction \	ANN Model A (Training)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	398	11	43	3	87.47
AN	52	389	9	0	86.45
TNT	11	12	412	0	94.71
Soil	0	3	0	457	99.34
Reference Prediction \	ANN Model A (Testing)				
Class	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	82	34	27	2	56.55
AN	47	88	13	2	58.66
TNT	21	12	119	13	72.12
Soil	0	3	6	134	93.70

Table 5.7: Confusion Matrix of ANN model B on optimal wavelengths

Reference Prediction \ Class	ANN Model B (Training)				
	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	223	133	53	31	50.69
AN	112	302	39	2	66.37
TNT	32	5	381	39	83.37
Soil	2	1	42	403	89.96

Reference Prediction \ Class	ANN Model B (Testing)				
	C4	AN	TNT	Soil	Accuracy
C4	73	60	23	5	45.34
AN	37	95	10	1	66.44
TNT	7	4	123	13	83.67
Soil	1	0	10	138	92.61

Table 5.8: Accuracy assessment of ANN model on full spectra (ANN Model A) and ANN model on optimal wavelength (ANN Model B)

	Training			Testing		
	Accuracy	RMSE	Kappa	Accuracy	RMSE	Kappa
Model A	0.92	0.34	0.89	0.71	0.43	0.64
Model B	0.72	0.75	0.64	0.72	0.42	0.62

Figure 5.11: Accuracy assessment of ANN model on full spectra (ANN Model A) and ANN model on optimal wavelength (ANN Model B)

5.3.6 Comparison of ANN, RF and SVM Classification Model on Virgin Datasets

The virgin test images are generated inside the laboratory to check the accuracy of the SVM model created in the previous section. The Figure 5.12 (a) is the image of the chemical samples taken by the camera and Figure 5.12 (b) is plotted in R using colour composite where band number 85, 50 and 30 were assigned to RGB respectively. For testing the accuracy of the model pixels were labelled for different chemicals and for soil. The cell number and XY of the labelled pixels were saved and compared with the predicted label of the selected pixels. The classified image is shown in Figure 5.12 (c) where the red pixels shows the presence of the chemical while green shows the soil and background pixels. Similarly, another test image was taken as shown in Figure 5.13 (a) where the first and third petri dishes shows the mixture of chemical and soil whereas second petri dish shows pure chemical, fourth petri dish shows the soil sample. The developed SVM model was used to predict the traces of chemicals and the classification result is shown in Figure 5.13 (c). The red pixels show the presence of chemical and green shows the soil and background. SVM followed by ANN was proved to be best techniques for detecting the traces of chemicals in hyperspectral image out of three machine learning algorithms applied on test dataset in this study as shown in Figure 5.14. The model developed using the wavelengths selected from PCA is useful for trace detection. The second-best model was developed using ANN. The SVM algorithm created hyperplane with maximum margin due to which the prediction error was reduced. SVM gave satisfactory results in a less execution time of 8 minutes which is 300% less than execution time of ANN model. ANN model is more vulnerable to outliers and need a greater number of variables to perform better as compared to SVM. Model developed using RF had an intermediate result in comparison to other prediction models. “RF is an ensemble classifier and has the goodness of decision tree system. The order of performance of the machine learning algorithms used in this study with respect to accuracy is as follows (SVM > ANN > RF) and the order of performance of the model based on execution time is as follows (SVM > RF > ANN). The average user and producer accuracy on virgin datasets for all the three model are shown in Figure 5.15.

Figure 5.12 (a), (b) and (c): Trace detection of chemical when mixed with soil

Figure 5.13 (a), (b) and (c): Trace detection of chemical when mixed with soil

Figure 5.14: Comparison of SVM, ANN and RF Model

Figure 5.15 Comparison of Model using SVM, ANN and RF on Test Dataset

5.4 Discussion

In this study BaySpec OCI-F hyperspectral sensor is used which has an advantage of storing the spectral response of the target into 144 bands over the spectrum of 400-1000 nm at a spectral resolution of 4.16 nm. High spectral resolution of HSI is a great advantage over standard MSS as it allows to study the response at larger number of bands. Existing techniques like raman spectrometry or ion or mass spectrometry also have an advantage of higher spectral resolution, but the spatial coverage of these techniques are low due to single laser point on the sample. HSI comes with an advantage of both spectral and spatial coverage but with these pros HSI also faces a great challenge of high dimensional data and data redundancy. (Silva et al., 2017) in his articles has discussed the disadvantages of high dimensionality and techniques to reduce the dimensionality. In this research the spectral response of the target is stored is 144 bands which increases the computational cost when data analysis is performed. Response stored in the neighbouring bands are highly correlated and therefore all 144 bands do not carry unique information to determine the target (Xing et al., 2007). Data redundancy can be reduced using the techniques like PCA and first derivative. These two techniques have been applied on hyperspectral images in several research and have showed satisfactory results. PCA and first derivative was applied on the research studies for characterization of milk powder (Munir et al., 2018), image analysis of strawberries (Zhang et al., 2016), study germination of native seeds (Nansen et al., 2015), provenance discrimination and indicator for mineral exploration (Makvandi et al., 2019), analysis of polymer bank notes (Lim and Murukeshan, 2017). PCA and first derivative was applied on the spectral response of the chemicals derived from the hyperspectral images, 22 bands were selected from the 144 bands which carried most important and unique information with a variance of 90%. The high value of variance explains that 90% of the information from the 144 bands were retained in the 22 selected bands. Data analysis and image processing on these 22 selected bands reduce the computational time which increases the efficiency of the system. Data reduction techniques is important to be applied in HSI because it carries information in three dimension which increases the size of the data matrix which needs to be analysed. In Figure 5.16 size of data matrix is shown for hyperspectral, multispectral and raman spectroscopy for 10*10 pixel where each pixel size is 1cm. Therefore for 100 cm² area hyperspectral imaging system will store data in [10*10*144], where as a MSS with 10 bands will store data as [10*10*10] and raman spectroscopy will store as [1*144] if spectral resolution is same. Since raman spectroscopy lacks the spatial coverage the data matrix for this case will remain always the same hence data reduction is not a major concern for this technique. But as shown in Figure 5.16 the data size of hyperspectral sensors increases exponentially as compared to multispectral. Therefore, data reduction performed using PCA and first derivative reduced the number of spectral bands for analysis by 85 % which is very significant without loss of much information and is a widely accepted method for image processing of hyperspectral images.

Figure 5.16: Size of data for different imaging techniques

Previous studies for trace detection techniques were not standoff as most of them had to come in contact with the samples (Zapata et al., 2016) and the analysis were performed inside the laboratory on the collected samples from the crime scene. Most of these techniques saw the drawbacks like portability to crime scene, heavy and difficult to transport, no spatial coverage. The collected samples undergo degradation or gets destroyed during the experiments performed making these techniques destructive in nature. These destruction takes place due to high intensity of the laser beams on single point of samples or due to ionization process or mixing the samples with other chemicals. The overall accuracy of these techniques is greater than 90% but it comes with several disadvantages discussed above. The applicability of these techniques on the field is low as compared to HSI. The techniques HSI which is proposed in this study overcomes the drawback of most of these techniques making it more feasible for carrying out near real time ground operations with minimum human interference. HSI achieves an accuracy greater than 70% and provides advantages like portability, non-destructive nature, high spatial and spectral coverage and standoff trace detection. According to the experts of forensic lab 70% accuracy is an acceptable result as it

can complement other techniques like GPR and magnetometer which would increase the performance of the system. A survey with the forensic experts shows their preference for HSI over existing techniques.

Supervised image classification on remote sensing data set is an example of ML integrated with remote sensing. In this study various ML algorithms like SVM, RF and ANN were tested on the hyperspectral image to check the performance. In previous studies on integration of ML with remote sensing very few researches have applied SVM, ANN or RF for trace detection of chemicals. Most of the studies using ML and HSI were applied in different research fields like food quality assessment (Lim and Murukeshan, 2017), distribution of heavy metals in agricultural soil (Tan et al., 2019), classification of defective potatoes (Ji et al., 2019). It is important to test different ML algorithms for research study because the performance varies with the type and quantity of data required for training the model. Performance of the model can be evaluated using various factors like accuracy, user and producer accuracy, execution time. There is always a trade-off between the factors, and it depends on the user to select which factor is more important for its application. For example, if user wants higher accuracy for trace detection, they would choose ANN over SVM but if user wants fast processing and reduce execution time they would prefer SVM. Therefore, user can select the algorithm based on the phase of the project. Previous techniques like raman spectroscopy, IMS which were used for trace detection do not integrate machine learning in their analysis. Machine learning for HSI works as a classification technique where trained algorithm identifies the traces of chemicals on the soil as a background. Whereas in RS or IMS there is no need of image classification as they work on the principal of identifying the chemicals based on molecular structure by performing chemical or molecular degradation or ionization techniques. Therefore, integrating ML for trace detection of chemical using hyperspectral sensor is a novel approach and gives several advantages over traditional techniques.

5.5 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, PCA and first derivative approach were applied to reduce the dimensionality of the hyperspectral data. The techniques were implemented on the spectrum response to determine the 22 optimal wavelengths out of 144 wavelengths which have more importance. High dimensionality of the hyperspectral data is a curse which was resolved using PCA and first derivative. In later part of the chapter several classification models were developed using SVM, ANN and RF. Models were developed using original dataset which contains 144 wavelengths and also on reduced dataset which contains 22 wavelengths. Accuracy assessment of all the models are performed using overall accuracy, user accuracy, producer accuracy and confusion matrix. Developed SVM model produced an accuracy of 86.48 % in training phase and 81.11 % in testing phase with an execution time of 15 and 8 minutes. The model also had high selectivity since it was able to discriminate between the different classes with an accuracy of more than 70%. The average user and producer accuracy for TNT, C4, AN and Soil were determined to be 62.90, 70.76, 77.46, 91.40 and 66.19, 67.62, 78.57, 96.19. ANN model was also developed to study the comparison with SVM. The developed ANN model produced an accuracy of 92% in the training phase and 72% in testing phase with an execution time of 135 and 32 minutes. The average user and producer accuracy of TNT, C4, AN and soil were 65.44, 68.78, 74.46, 95.67 and 67.62, 61.90, 81.90, 91.90. The developed RF model performed with an execution time of 41 and 16 minutes. The average user and producer accuracy of TNT, C4, AN and soil were 62.84, 67.89, 74.90, 93.02 and 44.29, 70.48,

92.38, 95.24. On comparing three model it was observed that SVM model showed higher selectivity and less execution time. The overall accuracy of the model was 78% and 75% and 71% respectively.

CHAPTER 6

DETERMINING ALTITUDE OF SENSOR AND MINIMUM MAPPING SIZE OF CHEMICAL

6.1 Introduction

A key issue for identifying traces of chemical in the hyperspectral image from remotely sensed data is the identification of the minimum mapping size of the pure chemical. Identifying the minimum size of the traces of the target chemical determines the accuracy of the model at different altitude. Classified maps derived from remotely sensed data are often presented using a minimum mapping unit (MMU). An MMU is defined as “the smallest size areal entity to be mapped as a discrete entity”.

Determining minimum size of the pure chemical for trace detection of chemical for different spatial resolution and MMU in hyperspectral image is an important consideration due to the problem of mix pixel where a pixel can be dominated by the background material. If the quantity of the trace of the chemical is less than the background material in the pixel in that case mix pixel problem would arise. This results in identification of pixels which contain mixture of chemical and background material specially on the edges of the chemical which reduces the overall accuracy. Inappropriate size of minimum mapping size of chemical results into “salt and pepper” effect where there exist many single pixels of a target chemical that are interspersed with contiguous areas of other background material. Individual pixels are not spectrally pure because diffuse directional reflectance from neighboring pixels contribute to a given pixel’s spectral signature. Such problem can be resolved by using appropriate size of minimum mapping size of chemical. Whereas if the minimum mapping size of chemical is small then problem of mix pixel problem is reduced as only pure pixels containing chemicals will be identified. Traces of chemicals that are sparse and fragmented can be considerably misrepresented in the final map when increasing minimum mapping size of chemical, while the classes that occupy a large percentage of map area tend to become more dominant. Given the preceding information, the choice of an appropriate MMU is clearly important. The suggested mapping size should provide as much information as possible at a minimum economic cost, without losing necessary spatial information (Xiangyun et al. 2005). Hence, both precision and cost are factors that can have an effect on the final selection of the minimum mapping size of chemical but ideally the suggested size falls within the constraints of the economics.

This chapter focuses on determining the minimum mapping size of chemical for trace detection of chemicals used in explosives based on the constraint of altitude of the sensor. The results of the experiments performed in this next section would indicate that altitude of the sensor and minimum mapping size of chemical which has a significant effect on accuracy when both the variables were changed by relatively large amounts. Results obtained from the experiments leave the user with a flexible range of altitude and MMU that are appropriate for different applications.

6.2 Methodology

As was mentioned above, the objective of this chapter was to determine and suggest the altitude of sensor and minimum mapping size of pure chemical for finding traces of chemicals as shown in conceptual Figure 6.1 (a). The approach used to achieve this objective is shown in Figure 6.1(b) and Figure 6.2. The experiments were conducted in outdoor conditions and suitable altitude and minimum mapping size of the chemicals were identified using the SVM model and spectral library developed in the previous chapter. Chemical samples were prepared in different sizes which varied from 0.25*0.25 cm to 1cm*1cm as shown in Figure 6.1(b). The dimensions of the chemical samples were measured accurately using the measuring instruments and distributed over the soil. The hyperspectral sensor was placed on the vehicle at different altitude varying from 40cm to 150cm. Speed of the vehicle is determined using the in-built software of the sensor. Speed is suggested to user depending upon the side overlap the user has requested for the mentioned altitude. These chemical samples were placed over the soil samples and marked with different colors for accuracy assessment in later part of the experiment. Hyperspectral cube was created for the chemical samples at different heights using pushbroom scanning. To detect the traces of the chemicals, present in the hyperspectral cube, the image is converted into tiff format which goes as an input to the SVM model developed in previous chapter using the spectral library. The SVM model determines the traces of the chemical samples present and accuracy assessment is done for all the images acquired at different altitude of the sensor. The suitable altitude is selected for the next experiment where the altitude is fixed and the MMU size of the chemicals are varied. Hyperspectral cube is generated and the SVM model is used to determine how many samples of each MMU were detected correctly and incorrectly.

Figure 6.1(a): Conceptual design for the experiments to be conducted

Figure 6.1(b): Steps for conducting experiment to suggest altitude of sensor in outdoor conditions

Figure 6.2: Conceptual design of method to determine suitable minimum mapping size of pure chemical used in explosives

Conceptual design of the experiment is shown in the Figure 6.3 which gives information how experiment was conducted in terms of varying the altitude of the sensor and size of the chemical samples. In the Figure 6.3 blue cylinder represents the hyperspectral camera whose altitude is varied from 40cm to 150cm and in yellow color the chemical samples of different size are represented.

Figure 6.3: Conceptual design of the experiment

6.3 Results

Spatial resolution of the hyperspectral image acquired at different heights are shown in Table 6.1. The results of the classification accuracy for individual chemicals using the SVM model developed previously are presented. Area of soil is kept same throughout the experiments and minimum mapping unit was varied from 0.25cm, 0.33 cm, 0.50 cm and 1cm as shown in Table 6.2.

Table 6.1 show that, as the altitude of the sensor size was increased, the overall percent accuracy value decreased in a linear nature. Table 6.2 shows how the accuracy of the detection of chemical increase when the minimum mapping unit is increased. The accuracy estimates increased gradually until the MMU reached 0.5 cm at which point the curve began to level off. The likely explanation for the slowing rate of increase in the accuracy estimates is that the MMU became sufficiently large that a smaller percentage of areas. From the results an accuracy of more than 75% can be achieved when the sensor is placed at a height of 90cm and similarly the chemical sample with size of 0.5 cm to 1cm gave desirable results whereas samples of size less than 0.5 cm gave low accuracy. Therefore, suggested height for placing the sensor on the vehicle can be around 90 cm and the minimum mapping unit can be selected as 0.5cm.

Table 6.1: Determines the accuracy of chemical at different height of sensors

Altitude (cm)	Spatial Resolution (cm)	No. of Pixels	Accuracy (%)
40	0.012	1569	79.73 ± 0.02
60	0.018	784	78.14 ± 0.02
90	0.027	523	76.49 ± 0.03
120	0.036	392	72.11 ± 0.05
150	0.045	313	67.18 ± 0.04

Figure 6.4: Accuracy of chemical at different altitude of sensors

Table 6.2: Determining accuracy for different sample size of chemicals

Sample size (cm)	No. of Pixels	Spatial Resolution (cm)	Accuracy (%)
1	38	0.028	79.00 ± 0.02
0.5	19	0.028	72.77 ± 0.04
0.33	13	0.028	54.94 ± 0.04
0.25	9	0.028	48.69 ± 0.10

Figure 6.5: Mapping accuracy for different size of chemical samples

Following are the results about determining the speed of the sensor for different altitude. According to the manufacture of the sensor the suggested speed is based upon the percentage of side overlap user wants. The SpecGrabber which is the software used for controlling the sensor calculates the suggested speed based on the altitude, field of view, swath and consider side overlap as 70%. Table 6.3 shows the result for the suggested speed calculated by the software for different altitude. In similar way speed is calculated for different altitude and different overlap percentage as shown in Table 6.4. User can select the speed from the Table 6.4 based on their requirement of overlap. Figure 6.6 shows the suggested speed and Figure 6.7 shows the minimum, maximum and suggested speed.

Table 6.3: Altitude and suggested speed for sensors

Altitude (cm)	Suggested Speed (cm/s)
40	4.7
60	7.0
90	10.5
120	14.0
150	17.5

Figure 6.6: Suggested speed for different altitude

Table 6.4: Determining speed (cm/s) for various overlapping % at different altitude

Altitude (cm)	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%
40	7.8	6.2	4.7	3.1	1.6
60	11.6	9.3	7.0	4.7	2.3
90	17.5	14.0	10.5	7.0	3.5
120	23.3	18.6	14.0	9.3	4.7
150	29.1	23.3	17.5	11.6	5.8

Figure 6.7: Minimum, suggested and maximum speed for different altitude

In Table 6.5 discusses about flight time and number of raw images the sensor will store when scanning an area of 10m² at a speed of 10.5 cm/s at different altitude.

Table 6.5: Determining number of images, storage and flight time at 10.5 cm/s

Altitude (cm)	Speed (cm/s)	No. of Images	Storage (GB)	Flight Time (min)
40	10.5	1728	21.25	26
60	10.5	768	9.45	17
90	10.5	285	3.5	11
120	10.5	195	2.2	10
150	10.5	130	1.6	8

6.4 Discussion

Effect of altitude of the sensor and spatial resolution on the overall accuracy of the SVM classification model has been shown in the previous section. Based on the results obtained from different experiments conducted in this chapter it was observed that the image with a finer resolution achieved higher accuracy but at a lower altitude which might not be feasible in real applicability. Whereas images collected at a coarser resolution but at a height of 150 cm achieved an accuracy of around 65% because the images contained traces of different chemical and soil as background. Therefore, with increase in altitude the dominance of the reflectance in the pixel was more from soil instead of pure chemicals which leads to decrease in accuracy and misclassification. The misclassification error can be grouped as pure pixel classification error or mixed pixel classification error. Mixed pixel between the soil and the chemical was the major reason for lower accuracy. To determine the suggested MMU for trace detection of chemicals. The spatial resolution of the image was kept fixed and the pixels were subdivided into 0.5, 0.33 and 0.25 cm MMU. For studying the effect of MMU on the accuracy the image of chemical at resolution of 0.028 cm at an altitude of 90 cm, consisting of 38 pixels was reduced to 19, 13 and 9 pixels. As discussed earlier the misclassification occurred due to mixed pixel where a pixel is made up of from two or more classes. This kind of error occurs often in the boundaries between two classes and is also referred to as boundary effect. From the results it can be seen and discussed that when the MMU was 1 cm in that case 30 pixels out of 38 pixels were correctly classified whereas the pixels around the boundary were misclassified. Similarly, for 0.5 MMU the 14 pixels out of 19 were misclassified and similarly pixels around the boundary which had dominance of soil were misclassified. But when MMU was decreased to 0.25 cm 4 pixels out of 9 were only classified correctly.

For practical applicability of the hyperspectral imaging system, the user needs to decide the altitude and MMU according to the accuracy they want to achieve which could be screening phase or critical phase. One of the major factors which affects the real applicability is the amount of storage required, processing time for creation of hyperspectral cube. Speed of the vehicle mounted with sensor determines coverage area in a given time and number of raw images that would be acquired. From the experiment firstly suitable altitude was determined. 90 cm is the suggested altitude for the user as it is easier to deploy a sensor at an altitude 90 cm rather than 40 cm, 60 cm on an automated vehicle. The coverage area or swath at 40 cm, 60 cm is comparatively low to 90 cm. At 90 cm the user can expect an accuracy of more than 75% which would decrease if the altitude is increased to 150 cm. 90 cm to 120 cm can be suggested altitude for the sensor to be deployed in real ground application. After determining a suitable height of 90 cm, suitable MMU was determined (0.5 cm) as the accuracy achieved was more than 70% and it had minimal effect of mixed pixel problem if compared to 0.33 cm to 0.25 cm, later two MMU had a very low accuracy almost equal to 50%. For 90 cm height the speed can be varied from 3.5 cm/s to 17.5 cm/s depending upon the required overlapping by the user. Suggested overlapping is 70% which results in a uniform stitching in the raw images for creation of hyperspectral cube. For 70% overlap the suggested speed is 10.5 cm/s whereas it could be 17.5 cm/s for 50% overlap and 3.5 cm/s for 90% overlap. For real ground conditions controlling the automated vehicle at 3.5 cm/s is not feasible as it would take a much higher time to cover the area of interest. If the vehicle is moving at a speed of 10.5 cm/s to cover an area of 10 m² at altitude of 90 cm, the system would acquire 285 raw images with storage of 3.5 GB whereas if the altitude is 60 cm the system would acquire 768 raw images with storage of 9.45 GB

which is more expensive and not feasible when size of the area is increased. On the basis of several calculation and discussions with final users it was decided that (90-120 cm) altitude, 0.5 cm MMU and 10.5 cm/s speed is highly suggested for practical usage of hyperspectral imaging system.

6.5 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, suggested altitude for the sensor was determined for increasing the accuracy of model. Similarly, minimum mapping unit of chemical sample was determined at the suggested altitude. To determine the suggested altitude the and minimum size of the chemical that can be detected in the acceptable range of accuracy several experiments were performed in real ground conditions. This chapter focuses on the applicability of the proposed method in the real world. In the first set of experiment the altitude of the sensor was varied from 40 cm to 150 cm and the accuracy of the model was determined. From the analysis it was found that altitude that should be suggested was 90 cm where accuracy was more than 75%. In the second set of experiment minimum size of chemical sample was varied from 0.25 cm to 1cm. The accuracy of the model was more than 70% when the minimum sample size was 0.5 cm or greater. For various altitude suggested speed of the vehicle were calculated. Therefore, to implement hyperspectral imaging system on the unarmed vehicle for real application, the suggested altitude and speed of the sensor should be around 90 cm and 10.5 cm/s at which detection limit would be equal or more than 0.5 cm with accuracy greater than 70%.

CHAPTER 7 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

7.1 Conclusion

Terrorist bombings using the explosives containing nitrate like TNT, RDX, PETN has led to deaths of 25,673 deaths, and global economic loses of US\$84 billion in 2016 only (Peace, 2017) making it a global issue. Storage and disposal of the explosive chemicals has led to environmental issue, endangering health and safety of the public making it a major concern worldwide (Che et al., 2012, Sulzer et al., 2012). Though there are number of researches focused on bulk detection and trace detection of explosives using spectroscopy and similarly, hyperspectral remote sensing and microwave remote sensing have been used in several research for bulk detection of explosives like landmines or metallic targets. Researchers have come up with new techniques like Raman spectroscopy, SERS, LIBS, MS, IMS for trace detection of explosives but very few works have been done for standoff trace detection using hyperspectral remote sensing. Recently some research has been published using hyperspectral imaging system in the field of forensic for determine traces of explosives at crime scene or bank notes. Most of the existing techniques for trace detection are heavy, complex, expensive and non-portable making them not suitable for field applications. One of the major challenges faced by stand-off trace detection is discrimination between the traces of explosives and background material.

Spectral response acquired by hyperspectral sensor helps in discriminating between the explosives and soil effectively in between 400 nm to 1000 nm. Spectral response of chemicals like TNT, C4, ANFO, soil and vegetation were stored in a database called spectral library which was used for trace detection of explosives in the image collected from the field. The library developed was used to discriminate between explosive and soil and classify the explosives into TNT, C4, ANFO. Hyperspectral sensor used in the research produced the spectral response at a spectral resolution of 4.16 nm in between the spectrum of 400-1000 nm and spatial resolution at 0.012 cm at 40 cm height.

One of major advantage of HSI over the other existing techniques is three-dimensional information which includes spectral resolution in Z axis and spatial information in XY. The 3D information helped in identifying the chemicals based on spectral response in 144 band and determining the spatial position. By making the spatial resolution finer the challenge of average areal density is overcome due to which the spectral response is collected from the pure pixel of chemical and background material making it easy to identify.

Along with all advantages hyperspectral sensor faces the curse of high dimensionality since the spectral response is saved in 100's of bands as compared to multi spectral where it is saved in 4-10 bands. Since the spectral response is saved at every 4.16 nm there is high probability that the contiguous bands are correlated resulting in repetitive information. It is important to determine which wavelength carries unique information and reduce the dimensionality of data to reduce the processing cost. PCA and first derivative are efficient methods to reduce the dimensionality and determine the optimal wavelengths. Reduction of 84% in number of bands was observed in the study (from 144 to 22 optimal bands). 22 optimal bands were determined by analysing the loading score of principal components and by computing first derivative of spectral response of the

chemicals. Use of HSI along with machine learning algorithms is in itself an original work. Several algorithms like SVM, ANN, RF were applied in the study to determine the most suitable for trace detection based on accuracy and execution time. Developed SVM model produced an accuracy of 86.48 % in training phase and 81.11 % in testing phase with an execution time of 15,8 minutes. The model also had high selectivity since it was able to discriminate between the different classes with an accuracy of more than 70 %. The average user and producer accuracy on virgin datasets for TNT, C4, AN and Soil were determined to be 62.90, 70.76, 77.46, 91.40 and 66.19, 67.62, 78.57, 96.19. ANN model was also developed to study the comparison with SVM. The developed ANN model produced an accuracy of 92 % in the training phase and 72% in testing phase with an execution time of 135 and 32 minutes. The average user and producer accuracy on virgin datasets of TNT, C4, AN and soil were 65.44, 68.78, 74.46, 95.67 and 67.62, 61.90, 81.90, 91.90. On comparing all three models it was observed that SVM model showed higher selectivity and less execution time. The overall accuracy of the SVM, ANN and RF model on the virgin datasets were 78%, 75% and 71% respectively. To determine the suggested height of sensor, the height of the sensor was increased from 40 cm to 150 cm. The accuracy of the model decreased linearly with increase in the height. According to the feasibility of placing the sensor on the vehicle in real ground conditions with tradeoff of accuracy 90 cm at a speed of 10.5 cm/s was selected as the suggested height. The model produced an accuracy of 76.49 %, whereas the model produced an accuracy of 67.18% at a height of 150cm.

To determine the minimum mapping unit of the chemical the sample size was varied from 0.25cm to 1cm. The accuracy for different MMU increased gradually until the MMU reached 0.5 cm at which point the curve began to level off. The chemical sample with size of 0.5 cm to 1cm gave desirable results whereas samples of size less than 0.5 cm gave low accuracy. Therefore, suggested height and speed for placing the sensor on the vehicle can be around 90 cm, 10.5 cm/sec and the minimum mapping unit can be selected as 0.5cm.

HSI for the trace detection of explosives a new technique which provides several advantages over other existing techniques like portability to crime scene, easy for field applications due to its less complexity and less weight. The system can be used for pre and post explosion analysis. The primary survey for identifying the traces of the chemicals can be performed in a target area. For the post event analysis the concentration of the chemical varies with distance from the crime spot. Since technique provides standoff trace detection it increases the safety of the operator, reducing the risk of life. The HSI technique doesn't use laser for exciting the samples, or do not covert the states of matter of samples for analysis due to which it is non-destructive in nature. With all the above-mentioned advantages whole system provides high selectivity when used with SVM. This technique gives the ability to remotely identify the composition of each pixel of the generated image (Smekens and Gouhier, 2018). The fast, non-invasive, non-destructive and contactless characteristic of HSI makes it a promising standoff trace detection tool as it provides remote and real time measurements.

In this study, we examined the potential of hyperspectral imaging system combined with machine learning algorithms for rapid and non-destructive assessment for standoff trace detection of explosives. The hyperspectral imaging system developed for trace detection in this study is unique and only few researches using similar approach have been published. Creating a spectral library of the chemicals used in explosives based to their spectral reflectance is a different approach of

identifying the chemicals as compared to the existing techniques. The standoff detection approach of the HSI has significant contribution in the technology of detection of explosives by reducing the threat of life of the operator. Large number of research articles have been published on the use of machine learning techniques for different fields but significantly very few articles integrating machine learning techniques on hyperspectral images for trace detection of explosive chemicals can be found. HSI has been used in several applications for food quality, agriculture, detecting macronutrients, forensic science but trace detection of explosives using HSI and machine learning algorithms is in itself an original work. Therefore, the research and its outcome will work as the baseline work for such types of research. A unique research framework was designed in this study where use of several ML algorithms trained on the developed spectral library was used for trace detection in real field conditions under the sunlight. To increase the efficiency of the whole system, high dimensionality of the hyperspectral images was reduced using PCA and first derivative. The proposed methodology was able to detect some of the widely used explosives used in creation of IEDs worldwide, such as TNT, C4 and AN. Conventional technologies used for detecting the explosives makes use of separation techniques which consumes more time and require sample preparation, while HSI is a fast, non-invasive, non-destructive and non-contact technique which, in addition, avoids sample preparation. For the purpose of collecting hyperspectral images, halogen and infrared lamp, along with hyperspectral sensor were used. Following conclusions can be drawn based on the experiments conducted and the results:

- To obtain uniform distribution and intensity in the field of view of the sensor combination of halogen and infrared lamp should be used. The two artificial light sources cover the spectrum of 400-1000 nm which is essential for extracting information in both visible and infrared region.
- Hyperspectral imaging system can be used to extract information regarding spatial distribution and properties of the chemicals present in the image.
- The spectral reflectance of the non-explosives and explosive chemicals derived from the hyperspectral image are different in nature specially from 500nm – 975nm and they can be used for trace detection in further study.
- Optimal wavelength in distinguishing the chemicals can be determined by applying first derivatives and principal component analysis on the spectral reflectance of the respective chemical.
- TNT, C4 and AN can be identified based on their spectral reflectance using the spectral library created.
- Hyperspectral sensor has potential to identify hidden explosive materials, minimize the risk of operators and non-destructive technique to avoid sample destruction and is portable to crime scene.
- SVM is most suitable algorithm among ANN and Random Forest for trace detection. Accuracy of SVM model on reduced dataset has an increase of 9.7% and decrease of 75% in execution time.

- PCA and First derivative reduced the dimensionality of the dataset with 84% (original image has 144 bands, reduced Image has 22 bands). Accuracy of the model using reduced dataset decreased by 1% which is not a significant change with respect to execution time.
- Suggested altitude and speed of the sensor is 90 cm and 10.5 cm/sec at which minimum mapping unit is greater than 0.5 cm to achieve accuracy greater than 70%.

Therefore, for identifying chemical traces in the large scene of ground images we need SVM model built using the optimal wavelengths due to its less computational load. The results of the study support the high potential of hyperspectral imaging system along with support vector machine model for trace detection of explosives by overcoming the drawbacks of existing techniques (such being time consuming, heavy equipment's and destructive process). Suggested height for placing the sensor on the vehicle in the field to acquire the image can be around 90 cm and the minimum mapping unit can be selected as 0.5cm. We also conclude that the result obtained in this study can be used for reference. The contribution of the research is a) novel approach for standoff trace detection of chemicals b) Spectral library based on the spectral responses of some of the chemicals use in explosives c) determining 22 wavelengths that can be used to detect the chemicals. The research was limited to three types of explosive material which were available, and the spectral library was developed using the artificial light sources like halogen and infrared lamp with keeping soil as background material. Therefore, the outcomes from this research will work as a baseline for such types of standoff trace detection techniques. HSI technique with more high selectivity and sensitivity will be prominent asset for defence and forensics.

7.2 Recommendation

The study made an attempt to develop a standoff trace detection technique for determining chemicals present on the ground surface. The following recommendations are made in context of this study for further research:

- There are many other chemicals like HMX, PETN, RDX which are used in explosives. Sample of these chemicals can be collected, and their spectral response can be saved in the developed spectral library.
- Chemicals like TNT goes under the process of degradation when exposed to sunlight for longer period. To overcome such challenges spectral response for degraded chemical can also be added to spectral library.
- Different background and surface can be added to the spectral library which would enhance the classification algorithm.
- Spectral response of the chemicals could be unique in the bandwidth of ultraviolet and thermal infrared and it would be interesting to study the characteristics. Hyperspectral sensor with larger bandwidth in the future could be used to do such analysis.
- Pixels present at the edges of the sample are often misclassified due to mixed pixels therefore, development of an algorithm is required to improve the accuracy.
- Snapshot hyperspectral camera can be used instead of pushbroom and it can be deployed on drone for wider coverage of area. Processing could be done image by image if the raw images are collected through snapshot camera.

- The selected 22 optimal bands can be used to develop a low cost of hyperspectral camera which could be used for trace detection.
- Research could be extended to map the concentration of chemical present using deep learning algorithms to determine the amount of chemical (in gm) present in the field of view.

References

- A.Hakonen, P.O.Andersson, M.S.Schmidt, T.Rindzevicius, M.Käll, Explosive and chemical threat detection by surface-enhanced Raman scattering: are- view, *Anal.Chim.Acta*893(2015)1–13.
- A.Hakonen, T.Rindzevicius, M.S.Schmidt, P.O.Andersson, L.Juhlin, M. Svedendahl, A.Boisen, M.Käll, Detection of nerve gases using surface- enhanced Raman scattering substrates with high droplet adhesion, *Nanoscale* 8 (2016)1305–1308.
- A.W. Fountain III, S.D. Christesen, R.P. Moon, J.A. Guicheteau, E.D. Emmons, Recent advances and remaining challenges for the spectroscopic detection of explosive threats, *Appl. Spectrosc.* 68 (2014) 795e811.
- Achal, S., McFee, J.E., Howse, J., 2010. Gradual dispersal of explosives by ants and its possible implication for future landmine production. In: *Proc. 7th International Symposium on Humanitarian Demining 2010*, Croatian Mine Action Center (CROMAC), Sibenik, Croatia, 27–29 April 2010, p. 60.
- Achal, S., McFee, J.E., Ivanco, T., Anger, C., 2007. A thermal infrared hyperspectral imager (tasi) for buried landmine detection. In: *Proc. SPIE Conference on Detection and Remediation Technologies for Mines and Mine-like Targets XII*, vol. 6553, Orlando, FL, USA, 9–13 April, 2007, pp. 655316-1-655316-11.
- Almeida, M.R., et al., 2015. Detection of explosives on the surface of banknotes by Raman hyperspectral imaging and independent component analysis. *Anal. Chim. Acta* 860,15–22.
- Axelsson, Maria, Friman, Ola, Haavardsholm, Trym Vegard, Renhorn, Ingmar, 2016. Target detection in hyperspectral imagery using forward modeling and in-scene information. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* 119, 124–134
- Bajjouk, T., Mouquet, P., Ropert, M., Quod, J., Hoarau, L., & Bigot, L. et al. (2019). Detection of changes in shallow coral reefs status: Towards a spatial approach using hyperspectral and multispectral data. *Ecological Indicators*, 96, 174-191. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.08.052
- Balas, C., Epitropou, G., Tsapras, A., & Hadjinicolaou, N. (2018). Hyperspectral imaging and spectral classification for pigment identification and mapping in paintings by El Greco and his workshop. *Multimedia Tools And Applications*, 77(8), 9737-9751. doi: 10.1007/s11042-017-5564-2
- Bousquet, O. and Elisseff, A.: Stability and generalization, *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, 2, 499–526, doi:10.1162/153244302760200704, 2002
- C. Wynn, S. Palmacci, R.R. Kunz, M. Aernecke, *Optical Express* 19 (19) (2011) 18671–18677.
- C. Wynn, S. Palmacci, R.R. Kunz, M. Rothschild, *Opt. Express* 18 (6) (2010) 5399–5406.
- C.I. Chang Orthogonal subspace projection (OSP) revisited: a comprehensive study and analysis *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 43 (3) (2005), pp. 502-518
- C.Martín-Alberca, C.García-Ruiz, Analytical techniques for the analysis of consumer fireworks, *TrendsAnal.Chem.*56(2014)27–36.

- Cavaignac, E., Savall, F., Chantalat, E., Faruch, M., Reina, N., Chiron, P., & Telmon, N. (2017). Geometric morphometric analysis reveals age-related differences in the distal femur of Europeans. *Journal of Experimental Orthopaedics*, 4(1). doi: 10.1186/s40634-017-0095-3
- Chaudhary, S., Ninsawat, S., & Nakamura, T. (2018). Non-Destructive Trace Detection of Explosives Using Pushbroom Scanning Hyperspectral Imaging System. *Sensors*, 19(1), 97. doi: 10.3390/s19010097
- Chen, D., Ramli, R., 2003. Contrast enhancement using recursive mean-separate histogram equalization for scalable brightness preservation. *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.* 49 (4), 1301–1309
- Crabtree, M. (2005). Hyperspectral One-Meter-Resolution Remote Sensing in Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming: I. Forage Nutritional Values. *Rangelands*, 58(5).
- D.S. Moore, Instrumentation for trace detection of high explosives, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 75 (2004) 2499.
- Duan, M., Gao, Q., Wan, Y., Li, Y., Guo, Y., & Ganzhu, Z. et al. (2012). Biomass estimation of alpine grasslands under different grazing intensities using spectral vegetation indices. *Canadian Journal Of Remote Sensing*, 37(4), 413-421. doi: 10.5589/m11-050
- Edelman, G.J., et al., 2012. Hyperspectral imaging for non-contact analysis of forensic traces. *Forensic Sci. Int.* 223 (1), 28–39.
- Elbasuney, S., El-Sherif, A.F., 2016. Complete spectroscopic picture of concealed explosives: laser induced Raman versus infrared. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 85 (Part B),34–41.
- El-Sharkawy, Y.H., Elbasuney, S., 2017. Novel laser induced photoacoustic spectroscopy for instantaneous trace detection of explosive materials. *Forensic Sci. Int.* 277 (SupplC), 215–222.
- Faust, A.A., Chesney, R.H., Das, Y., McFee, J.E., Russell, K.I., 2005. Canadian teleoperated landmine detection systems Part II: anti personal landmine detection”. *Int. J. Syst. Sci.* 36 (9), 529–543.
- Fernández de la Ossa, M.Á., García-Ruiz, C., Amigo, J.M., 2014. Near infrared spectral imaging for the analysis of dynamite residues on human handprints. *Talanta* 130, 315–321.
- Gao, J., Meng, B., Liang, T., Feng, Q., Ge, J., & Yin, J. et al. (2019). Modeling alpine grassland forage phosphorus based on hyperspectral remote sensing and a multi-factor machine learning algorithm in the east of Tibetan Plateau, China. *ISPRS Journal Of Photogrammetry And Remote Sensing*, 147, 104-117. doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.11.015
- García, P., Santoro, M., Singh, A., & Kedor-Hackmann, E. (2007). Determination of optimum wavelength and derivative order in spectrophotometry for quantitation of hydroquinone in creams. *Revista Brasileira De Ciências Farmacêuticas*, 43(3), 397-404. doi: 10.1590/s1516-93322007000300008
- Garroway, A.N., Buess, M.L., Miller, J.B., Suits, B.H., Hibbs, A.D., Barrall, G.A., Matthews, R., Burnett, L.J., 2001. Remote sensing by nuclear quadrupole resonance. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.* 39, 1108–1118.

- Giardino, C., Bresciani, M., Valentini, E., Gasperini, L., Bolpagni, R., Brando, V.E., 2015. Airborne hyperspectral data to assess suspended particulate matter and aquatic vegetation in a shallow and turbid lake. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 157, 48e57.
- H. Hernault, H. Prendinger, M. Ishizuka HILDA: A discourse parser using support vector machine classification *Dialogue Discourse* (2010), p. 1
- Hecker, C., van Ruitenbeek, F., Bakker, W., Fagbohun, B., Riley, D., van der Werff, H. and van der Meer, F. (2019). Mapping the wavelength position of mineral features in hyperspectral thermal infrared data. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 79, pp.133-140.
- Huovinen, P., Ramírez, J., & Gómez, I. (2018). Remote sensing of albedo-reducing snow algae and impurities in the Maritime Antarctica. *ISPRS Journal Of Photogrammetry And Remote Sensing*, 146, 507-517. doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.10.015
- Hou, W., Wang, J., Xu, X. and Reid, J. (2017). An algorithm for hyperspectral remote sensing of aerosols: 2. Information content analysis for aerosol parameters and principal components of surface spectra. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 192, pp.14-29.
- Hu, Y., Zou, L., Huang, X., & Lu, X. (2017). Detection and quantification of offal content in ground beef meat using vibrational spectroscopic-based chemometric analysis. *Scientific Reports*, 7(1). doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-15389-3
- I. Guyon, J. Weston, S. Barnhill, V. Vapnik Gene selection for cancer classification using support vector machines *Mach. Learning*, 46 (2002), pp. 389-422
- J. Yinon, *Counter terrorist Detection Techniques of Explosives*, Elsevier, Netherlands, 2007.
- J.D. White, F.A. Akin, H. Oser, D.R. Crosley, *Appl. Opt.* 50 (1) (2011) 74–81
- J.L. Gottfried, F.C. De Lucia, C.A. Munson, A.W. Miziolek, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.* 23 (2008) 205–216.
- J.S. Caygill, F. Davis, S.P.J. Higson, *Current trends in explosive detection techniques*, *Talanta* 88 (2012) 14–29
- Ji, Y., Sun, L., Li, Y., Li, J., Liu, S., Xie, X. and Xu, Y. (2019). Non-destructive classification of defective potatoes based on hyperspectral imaging and support vector machine. *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 99, pp.71-79.
- K.E. Brown, M.T. Greenfield, S.D. McGrane, D.S. Moore, *Advances in explosives analysis e part II: photon and neutron methods*, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 408 (2016) 49e65.
- K.L. Gares, K.T. Hufziger, S.V. Bykov, S.A. Asher, *Review of explosive detection methodologies and the emergence of standoff deep UV resonance Raman*, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 47 (2016) 124e141.
- Klunder, G., Nguyen, L., & Margalith, E. (2011). Near Infrared Spectral Imaging of Explosives Using a Tuneable Optical Parametric Oscillator Laser Source. *NIR News*, 22(3), 19-21. doi: 10.1255/nirn.1245

- Kruse, F.A., 2012. Mapping surface mineralogy using imaging spectrometry. *Geomorphology* 137 (1), 41e56.
- Lazic, V., et al., 2011. Detection of explosives in traces by laser induced breakdown spectroscopy: differences from organic interferents and conditions for a correct classification. *Spectrochim. Acta Part B: At. Spectrosc.* 66 (8), 644–655.
- Lelong, C.C., Pinet, P.C., Poilve, H., 1998. Hyperspectral imaging and stress mapping in agriculture: a case study on wheat in Beauce (France). *Remote Sens. Environ.* 66 (2), 179e191
- Lim, H. and Murukeshan, V. (2017). Hyperspectral imaging of polymer banknotes for building and analysis of spectral library. *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, 98, pp.168-175.
- M.A.Fernándezdela Ossa, J.M.Amigo,C.García-Ruiz, Detection of residues from explosive manipulation by near infrared hyperspectral imaging: a promising forensic tool, *ForensicSci.Int.*242(2014)228–235.
- M.Lopez-Lopez, C. García-Ruiz, Infrared and Raman spectroscopy techniques applied to identification of explosives, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 54 (2014) 36e44.
- M.Marshall, J.Oxley, Aspects of Explosives Detection, Elsevier, Netherlands, 2009.
- M.S. Colgan, C.A. Baldeck, J.-B. Féret, G.P. Asner Mapping savanna tree species at ecosystem scales using support vector machine classification and BRDF correction on airborne hyperspectral and LiDAR data *Remote Sens.*, 4 (2012), pp. 3462-3480
- Mahoney, C., Fahey, A., Steffens, K., Benner, B., & Lareau, R. (2010). Characterization of Composition C4 Explosives using Time-of-Flight Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. *Analytical Chemistry*, 82(17), 7237-7248. doi: 10.1021/ac101116r
- Makvandi, S., Beaudoin, G., Beth McClenaghan, M., Quirt, D. and Ledru, P. (2019). PCA of Fe-oxides MLA data as an advanced tool in provenance discrimination and indicator mineral exploration: Case study from bedrock and till from the Kiggavik U deposits area (Nunavut, Canada). *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 197, pp.199-211.
- María, and Carmen García-Ruiz. "Infrared And Raman Spectroscopy Techniques Applied To Identification Of Explosives." *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry* 54 (2014): 36-44. Web.
- McFee, J.E., Achal, S.B., Diaz, A.U., Faust, A.A., 2013. Comparison of broad-band and hyperspectral thermal infrared imaging of buried threat objects. In: *Proc. SPIE Conference on Detection and Sensing of Mines, Explosive Objects and Obscured Targets XVIII*, vol. 8709, Baltimore, MD, USA, 29 April–03 May 2013
- McFee, J.E., Faust, A.A., Das, Y., Russell, K.L., 2010. Final report Shield ARP 12 rl” – Optical imaging of explosive threats, August 2010.
- Meyer, R., Köhler, J., & Homburg, A. (2016). *Explosives*. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH.

- Mosca, S., Alberti, R., Frizzi, T., Nevin, A., Valentini, G., & Comelli, D. (2016). A whole spectroscopic mapping approach for studying the spatial distribution of pigments in paintings. *Applied Physics A*, 122(9). doi: 10.1007/s00339-016-0345-8
- Munir, M., Wilson, D., Yu, W., & Young, B. (2017). An evaluation of hyperspectral imaging for characterizing milk powders. *Journal Of Food Engineering*, 221, 1-10. doi: 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2017.10.001
- N. Nuntawong, P.Eiamchai, S.Limwichean, B.Wong-ek, M.Horprathum, V. Patthanasettakul, A.Leelapojanapom, S.Nakngoenthong, P.Chindaudom, Trace detection of perchlorate in industrial -grade emulsion explosive with portable surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy, *ForensicSci.Int.*233(2013) 174–178.
- Nansen, C., Zhao, G., Dakin, N., Zhao, C. and Turner, S. (2015). Using hyperspectral imaging to determine germination of native Australian plant seeds. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology*, 145, pp.19-24.
- National Research Council of the National Academies, Existing and Potential Standoff Explosives Detection Techniques, first ed., The National Academies Press, Washington, DC, 2004.
- Nubiato, K., Mazon, M., Antonelo, D., Calkins, C., Naganathan, G., Subbiah, J., & da Luz e Silva, S. (2018). A bench-top hyperspectral imaging system to classify beef from Nellore cattle based on tenderness. *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 89, 247-254. doi: 10.1016/j.infrared.2018.01.005
- O. Devos, C. Ruckebusch, A. Durand, L. Duponchel, J.-P. Huvenne Support vector machines (SVM) in near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy: focus on parameters optimization and model interpretation
- Orrillo, I., Cruz-Tirado, J., Cardenas, A., Oruna, M., Carnero, A., Barbin, D. and Siche, R. (2019). Hyperspectral imaging as a powerful tool for identification of papaya seeds in black pepper. *Food Control*, 101, pp.45-52.
- Osborne, S., Künnemeyer, R., Osborne, S., & Jordan, R. (1997). Method of Wavelength Selection for Partial Least Squares. *The Analyst*, 122(12), 1531-1537. doi: 10.1039/a703235h
- P.M. Pellegrino, E.L. Holthoff, M.E. Farrell, *Laser Based Optical Detection of Explosives*, first ed., Taylor & Francis Group, Boca Raton, FL, 2015.
- P.R.Laska, *Bombs, IEDs, and Explosives: Identification, investigation, and Disposal Techniques*,CRCPressTaylor&FrancisGroup,BocaRaton,USA,2016.
- R.S. Golightly, W.E.Doering, M.J.Natan, Surface-enhanced Ramanspectroscopy and homelandsecurity: a perfect match ? *ACSNano*3(2009) 2859–2869.
- S. Elbasuney, A.F. El-Sherif, Complete spectroscopic picture of concealed explosives: laser induced Raman versus infrared, *Trends Anal. Chem.* 85 (Part B) (2016) 34e41.
- S. Wallin, A. Pettersson, H. Ostmark, A. Hobro, Laser-based standoff detection of explosives: a critical review, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 395 (2009) 259e274.

- S.X. Li, Y.J. Zhang, Q.Y. Zeng, L.F. Li, Z.Y. Guo, Z.M. Liu, H.L. Xiong, S.H. Liu Potential of cancer screening with serum surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy and a support vector machine *Laser Phys. Lett.*, 11 (6) (2014)
- Scafutto, R., de Souza Filho, C., & de Oliveira, W. (2017). Hyperspectral remote sensing detection of petroleum hydrocarbons in mixtures with mineral substrates: Implications for onshore exploration and monitoring. *ISPRS Journal Of Photogrammetry And Remote Sensing*, 128, 146-157. doi: 10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2017.03.009
- Sengee, N., Sengee, A., Choi, H.K., 2010. Image contrast enhancement using bi- histogram equalization with neighborhood metrics. *IEEE Trans. Consum. Electron.* 56 (4).
- Serranti, S., et al., 2018. Characterization of microplastic litter from oceans by an innovative approach based on hyperspectral imaging. *Waste Manag.*
- Shao, Y., Xuan, G., Hu, Z., & Gao, X. (2018). Identification of adulterated cooked millet flour with Hyperspectral Imaging Analysis. *IFAC-Papersonline*, 51(17), 96-101. doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.08.068
- Sharma, Umesh Kumar, Kumawat, Kapil, 2015. Review of histogram based image contrast enhancement techniques. *Int. J. Res. Eng. Technol.* 3 (2), 2347–4599. ISSN(P), Feb 2015, 65-76.
- Silva, C., Pimentel, M., Amigo, J., Honorato, R., & Pasquini, C. (2017). Detecting semen stains on fabrics using near infrared hyperspectral images and multivariate models. *Trac Trends In Analytical Chemistry*, 95, 23-35. doi: 10.1016/j.trac.2017.07.026
- Smekens, J.-F., Gouhier, M., 2018. Observation of SO₂ degassing at Stromboli volcano using a hyperspectral thermal infrared imager. *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*
- Sohara, Y., Ryu, C., Suguri, M., Park, S. and Kishino, S. (2010). Estimation of Catechins Concentration of Green Tea Using Hyperspectral Remote Sensing. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 43(26), pp.172-177.
- Sun, C., Cao, S., & Sanchez-Azofeifa, G. (2019). Mapping tropical dry forest age using airborne waveform LiDAR and hyperspectral metrics. *International Journal Of Applied Earth Observation And Geoinformation*, 83, 101908. doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2019.101908
- Tan, K., Wang, H., Chen, L., Du, Q., Du, P. and Pan, C. (2019). Estimation the spatial distribution of heavy metal in agricultural soils using airborne hyperspectral imaging and random forest. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, p.120987.
- Vidal, M., Amigo, J.M., 2012. Pre-processing of hyperspectral images. Essential steps before image analysis. *Chemom. Intelligent Lab. Syst.* 117, 138e148.
- Wei, X., Liu, F., Qiu, Z., Shao, Y., He, Y., 2014. Ripeness classification of astringent persimmon using hyperspectral imaging technique. *Food Bioprocess Technol.* 7 (5), 1371e1380.
- Wen, P., et al., 2018 . Key challenges and prospects for optical standoff trace detection of explosives. *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem.* 100, 136–144.

- Willett, Rebecca M., Duarte, Marco F., Davenport, Mark A., Baraniuk, Richard G., 2014. Sparsity and structure in hyperspectral imaging: sensing, reconstruction, and target detection. *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* 31 (1), 116–126.
- Winter, Edwin M., Miller, Miranda A., Simi, Christopher G., Hill, Anthony B., Williams, Timothy J., Hampton, David, Wood, Mark, Zadnick, Jerry, Sviland, Marc D., 2004. Mine detection experiments using hyperspectral sensors. *Proc. SPIE* 5415, 1035–1041
- X.-Y. Wang, T. Wang, J. BuColor image segmentation using pixel wise support vector machine classification *Pattern Recogn.*, 44 (2011), pp. 777-787
- Xiangyun X, Gertner G, Wang G, Anderson B (2005) Optimal sampling scheme for estimation landscape mapping of vegetation cover. *Landscape Ecol* 20:375–387
- Xing, J., Saeys, W., & De Baerdemaeker, J. (2007). Combination of chemometric tools and image processing for bruise detection on apples. *Computers And Electronics In Agriculture*, 56(1), 1-13. doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2006.12.002
- Xu, Y., Chen, J. and Meng, P. (2019). Detection of alteration zones using hyperspectral remote sensing data from Dapingliang skarn copper deposit and its surrounding area, Shanshan County, Xinjiang Uygur autonomous region, China. *Journal of Visual Communication and Image Representation*, 58, pp.67-78.
- Y. Langeron, M. Doussot, D.J. Hewson, J. Duchene Classifying NIR spectra of textile products with kernel methods *Eng. Appl. Artif. Intell.*, 20 (3) (2007), pp. 415-427
- Y. Ma, G. Guo Support Vector Machines Applications Springer (2014)
- Zapata, F., de la Ossa, M., Gilchrist, E., Barron, L. and García-Ruiz, C. (2016). Progressing the analysis of Improvised Explosive Devices: Comparative study for trace detection of explosive residues in handprints by Raman spectroscopy and liquid chromatography. *Talanta*, 161, pp.219-227.
- Zhang, C., Guo, C., Liu, F., Kong, W., He, Y., & Lou, B. (2016). Hyperspectral imaging analysis for ripeness evaluation of strawberry with support vector machine. *Journal Of Food Engineering*, 179, 11-18. doi: 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2016.01.002
- Zhang, Yuxiang, Bo, Du, Zhang, Liangpei, 2015. A sparse representation-based binary hypothesis model for target detection in hyperspectral images. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.* 53 (3), 1346–1354